

MODERN EDUCATIONAL
SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE
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**MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND
INNOVATIVE TEACHING
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OLIV TALIM MUASSALARI TALABALARINING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Hamrayeva Oynisa Farxod qizi

Farg'ona davlat universiteti pedagogika kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

Kalit so'zlar: *Kommunikativ qobiliyat, individual psixologiya, pedagogika, kompetensiya, shaxsiy xususiyatlar, hamkorlik, muloqot, birgalikda boshqarish.*

Shaxsning kommunikativ faoliyatining tabiati uning kommunikativ qobiliyatiga, u tomonidan tan olingan kommunikativ qadriyatlarga, motivatsiya va muloqot ehtiyojlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga bog'liq. Shunday qilib, kommunikativ kompetensiya - bu muayyan shaxsning xatti-harakati va muloqotida individual psixologik, shaxsiy xususiyatlarda namoyon bo'ladigan yaxlit, nisbatan barqaror, yaxlit psixologik shakllanish. Kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlarini tushunishdagi farqga qaramay, barcha mualliflar, aslida, kommunikativ kompetensiya - bu boshqa odamlar bilan zarur aloqalarni o'rnatish va qo'llab-quvvatlash qobiliyati degan fikrga qo'shiladilar. 1.2 Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalarining kommunikativ kompetensiyasining xususiyatlari va uni o'qish davrida rivojlantirish zarurati Ijtimoiy turdagi kasblarda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning yuqori darajasi ayniqsa muhimdir, chunki muloqot kasbiy faoliyatning asosiy vositalaridan biridir. Ularsiz uning vazifalarini hal qilib bo'lmaydi. Muloqot madaniyatining bir qismi sifatida kommunikativ kompetensiya bo'lajak o'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratiga va muvaffaqiyatli kasbiy faoliyatiga erishish uchun zarur ijtimoiy-psixologik shartdir. Muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish - ijtimoiy-tarixiy amaliyot jarayonida shakllangan va muayyan shaxs mansub bo'lgan ijtimoiy-madaniy guruhda qabul qilingan muloqotning madaniy vositalari va aloqiy xatti-harakatlar normalarini o'zlashtirish jarayoni. Hozirgi vaqtda maktab amaliyotiga "hamkorlik", "muloqot", "birgalikda boshqarish" pedagogikasi g'oyalarini joriy etish sharoitida pedagogik faoliyatning kommunikativ tomoniga qo'yiladigan talablar muqarrar ravishda ortib bormoqda. Shu munosabat bilan oliy ta'limning dolzarb muammosi talabalarni samarali kasbiy-pedagogik muloqotga tayyorlashdir. Olimlar bu muammoni hal qilishdi va uni turli jihatlarida ko'rib chiqdilar. Shunday qilib, hatto qadimgi Yunonistonda ham sofistlar ishonitirish san'ati (dialektika) bilan bir vaqtda nutq san'atini ham o'rgatgan. Bunda ular amaliy foydalanishga g'amxo'rlik qilishdi. Muloqotning kommunikativ vazifasini hal qilish orqali kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish V.A. Kan-Kalik, A.V. Mudrik, N.V. Nikandrov va boshqalar. Kommunikativ kompetensiya omillari V.L. Zaxarov, Yu.Yu. Xryashchev. Kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlarini Yu.N. Emelyanov, Yu.M. Jukov, V.A.Labunskaya, kognitiv komponentni ta'kidlab.

Kommunikativ kompetentsiyaning hissiy komponenti eng muhim va murakkab komponent sifatida A.A.Bodalev, B.F. Lomov, B.G. Ananiev, M.I. Dyachenko, L.A. Kandybovich, V.A. Slastenin. Ijtimoiy psixologiyada muloqot tuzilishida uchta asosiy komponent yoki aspekt ajratiladi: kommunikativ almashinuv, o'zaro ta'sir va shaxsni shaxs tomonidan idrok etish.

Muloqot tuzilishi haqidagi ushbu g'oyadan kelib chiqadiki, kommunikativ kompetentsiya murakkab, ko'p qirrali shakllanishdir. Biz kommunikativ kompetentsiyani bilim, hissiy tajriba va aloqa vositalarida ravonlikka asoslangan shaxslararo muloqot sohasidagi qobiliyat va yo'nalish sifatida aniqlaymiz. Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurti o'z oldiga talabalarning kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish vazifasini qo'ygan holda, buning uchun o'quv dasturlari va maxsus o'qitish usullaridan foydalanishi mumkin. Shaxsning kommunikativ fazilatlarini shakllantirish uchun odamga o'z xatti-harakatlaridagi tendentsiyalarni ko'rib chiqish, uning motivlari va munosabatlarining xususiyatlarini tushunish imkonini beradigan ta'sir qilish usullari mos keladi. Shaxsning ijtimoiy-psixologik tuzilishiga ta'sir qilishning bunday usullariga, xususan, ijtimoiy-psixologik tayyorgarlik kiradi. O'quv mashg'ulotlarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishga ta'sirining nazariy asoslari G'arb psixologlari J. Moreno, C. Rogers, G. Shepardlarning tadqiqotlarida paydo bo'ldi. Keyinchalik mahalliy tadqiqotchilar ham ijtimoiy-psixologik tayyorgarlikning mumkin bo'lgan shakllarini ko'rib chiqib, turli asoslarga ko'ra tasniflashdi (M.R.Bityanova, L.A.Petrovskaya, V.V.Petrusinskiy, A.V.Fedotova va boshqalar). Talaba shaxsini bo'lajak oliy ma'lumotli mutaxassis sifatida rivojlantirish bir qancha yo'nalishlarda boradi: kasbiy yo'nalish mustahkamlanadi, zarur qobiliyatlar shakllanadi, takomillashtirilgan, "professionallashtirilgan" aqliy jarayonlar, holatlar, tajriba; burch hissi, kasbiy faoliyatning muvaffaqiyati uchun mas'uliyat; kasbiy mustaqillik va kelgusidagi amaliy ishlarga tayyorligi mustahkamlanadi. O'qituvchi oldida turgan vazifalardan kelib chiqqan holda, bo'lajak mutaxassisning kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish muammosiga mamlakatimizning ko'plab oliy o'quv yurtlarida namoyon bo'layotgan ilmiy qiziqishni tushunish mumkin. Kommunikativ kompetentsiya tarkibini o'rganish pedagogik ish uchun alohida amaliy ma'no kasb etadi, chunki muloqot unda faoliyat shakli sifatida amalga oshiriladi. Talaba uchun nafaqat o'qituvchilar, balki tengdoshlari bilan ham muloqot qilish qanchalik muhimligini ko'rsatadigan ko'plab faktlar to'plangan. O.V. Nikolaeva talabalar o'rtasida kommunikativ kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishning asosiy muammolarini ajratib ko'rsatdi: talabalar (ayniqsa, kichik o'quvchilar) tinglash qobiliyatiga ega emaslar. Shu bilan birga, talabalar hamkasbi tomonidan ilgari surilgan fikrni aniqlashtirish yoki davom ettirish zarur bo'lgan hollarda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi; talabalar ko'pincha ishbilarmonlik bilan muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlanmaganligini namoyish etadilar. Bu kam taniqli odamlar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil eta olmaslikda (ko'pincha

birinchi yilda), shuningdek, shaxsiy nuqtai nazardan yoqimsiz bo'lgan bunday stereotiplar bilan birgalikda o'quv vazifalarini bajarishni istamaslikda namoyon bo'ladi. vaqt. Bu xususiyat maktabda guruhda ishlash tajribasining etarli emasligining natijasidir. Ba'zi talabalar ta'limning guruh shakliga faqat universitetda duch kelganliklarini tan olishdi; · o'quv ma'lumotlaridan xabardorlik darajasi yuqori bo'lsa ham, darslar mazmunida talabalar savollarining ulushi etarli emas. Deyarli barcha o'qituvchilar talabalarni (to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita) savollarni shakllantirishga majbur qilish zarurati bilan duch kelishadi. Universitet bo'lajak o'qituvchilarini kommunikativ tayyorlashning ustuvor vazifasi monolog nutqidan va passiv tinglashdan dialogga o'tishdir; Ko'pchilik o'quvchilarning hayotiy tajriba va ilmiy bilimlardan foydalangan holda o'z nuqtai nazarini asosli, har tomonlama ifoda eta olmasligi do'zarb muammolardan biridir. Ko'pincha, bu kelajakdagi o'qituvchining nutqi, ongi yoki so'z boyligini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq emas, balki munozaralarda qatnashish tajribasining etishmasligi bilan izohlanadi. Talaba shaxsini bo'lajak oliy ma'lumotli mutaxassis sifatida rivojlantirish bir qancha yo'nalishlarda boradi: kasbiy yo'nalish mustahkamlanadi, zarur qobiliyatlar shakllanadi; takomillashtirilgan, "professionalashtirilgan" aqliy jarayonlar, holatlar, tajriba; burch hissi, kasbiy faoliyatning muvaffaqiyati uchun mas'uliyat; kasbiy mustaqillik va kelgusidagi amaliy ishlarga tayyorligi mustahkamlanadi. O'qituvchi oldida turgan vazifalardan kelib chiqqan holda, bo'lajak mutaxassisning kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish muammosiga mamlakatimizning ko'plab oliy o'quv yurtlarida namoyon bo'layotgan ilmiy qiziqishni tushunish mumkin. Kommunikativ kompetentsiya tarkibini o'rganish pedagogik ish uchun alohida amaliy ma'no kasb etadi, chunki muloqot unda faoliyat shakli sifatida amalga oshiriladi. Talaba uchun nafaqat o'qituvchilar, balki tengdoshlari bilan ham muloqot qilish qanchalik muhimligini ko'rsatadigan ko'plab faktlar to'plangan. Q.V. Nikolaeva talabalar o'rtasida kommunikativ kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishning asosiy muammolarini ajratib ko'rsatdi. Talabalar (ayniqsa, kichik o'quvchilar) tinglash qobiliyatiga ega emaslar. Shu bilan birga, talabalar hamkasbi tomonidan ilgari surilgan fikrni aniqlashtirish yoki davom ettirish zarur bo'lgan hollarda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi; · talabalar ko'pincha ishbilarmonlik bilan muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlanmaganligini namoyish etadilar. Bu kam taniqli odamlar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil eta olmaslikda (ko'pincha birinchi yilda), shuningdek, shaxsiy nuqtai nazardan yoqimsiz bo'lgan bunday stereotiplar bilan birgalikda o'quv vazifalarini bajarishni istamaslikda namoyon bo'ladi. vaqt. Bu xususiyat maktabda guruhda ishlash tajribasining etarli emasligining natijasidir. Ba'zi talabalar ta'limning guruh shakliga faqat universitetda duch kelganliklarini tan olishdi; · o'quv ma'lumotlaridan xabardorlik darajasi yuqori bo'lsa ham, darslar mazmunida talabalar savollarining ulushi etarli emas. Deyarli barcha o'qituvchilar talabalarni (to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita) savollarni shakllantirishga majbur qilish zarurati bilan duch kelishadi.

Universitet bo'lajak o'qituvchilarini kommunikativ tayyorlashning ustuvor vazifasi monolog nutqidan va passiv tinglashdan dialogga o'tishdir; Ko'pchilik o'quvchilarning hayotiy tajriba va ilmiy bilimlardan foydalangan holda o'z nuqtai nazarini asosli, har tomonlama ifoda eta olmasligi dolzarb muammolardan biridir. Ko'pincha, bu kelajakdagi o'qituvchining nutqi, ongi yoki so'z boyligini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq emas, balki munozaralarda qatnashish tajribasining etishmasligi bilan izohlanadi. Bu kamchilik, bizningcha, zamonaviy professional o'qituvchiga qo'yiladigan talablarning nihoyatda yuqori ekanligi bilan yanada kuchaydi. U nafaqat o'z pozitsiyasini to'g'ri bayon eta olishi, balki muloqotning tashkilotchisi va ishtirokchisi sifatida ishonchli, yorqin va o'ziga xos bo'lishi kerak.

1.3 Ijtimoiy-psixologik tayyorgarlik kommunikativ kompetentsiyani rivojlantirish sharti sifatida "Ijtimoiy-psixologik trening" atamasini nemis olimi M.Vorverg kiritgan. Bogomolova, tegishli ijtimoiy munosabatlarni faol shaklda shakllantirish sohasidagi ijtimoiy-psixologik bilimlarni o'zlashtirishdan iborat, ya'ni, maxsus ishlab chiqilgan tadbirlar jarayonida. Ijtimoiy va psixologik trening guruhleri insonning hissiy iliqlik va boshqa odam bilan aloqaga bo'lgan ehtiyojini tushunadi. Aynan shu erda, Rudestan K.ning so'zlariga ko'ra, "odam o'zini qabul qilingan va tushunilgan, ishonchli va ishonchli his qiladi, g'amxo'rlik va g'amxo'rlik bilan o'ralgan, yordam va yordam oladi". Shu kabi muammolar va tajribaga ega bo'lgan odamlarning yordami va qo'llab-quvvatlashi alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bunday qo'llab-quvvatlovchi va nazorat qilinadigan muhitda shaxshning o'zini o'zi kashf etishi va o'z-o'zini o'rganishi osonlashadi, buning uchun faqat muvaffaqiyatli o'rganish mumkin. Ijtimoiy-psixologik treningning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari quyidagilardan iborat: guruh ishining bir qator tamoyillariga rioya qilish, guruh a'zolarining o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishda psixologik yordamiga e'tibor qaratish, shu bilan birga bunday yordam nafaqat rahbar tomonidan, balki guruh a'zolarining o'zidan ham keladi; ko'proq yoki kamroq doimiy guruhning, ma'lum bir fazoviy tashkilotning mavjudligi (ko'pincha qulay, izolyatsiya qilingan xonada) ishlaydi, ishtirokchilar ko'p vaqtlarini aylanada o'tkazadilar), rivojlanadigan va faolroq bo'ladigan guruh a'zolari o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga urg'u "Bu erda va hozir" vaziyatida guruh ishining faol usullaridan foydalanish, guruh a'zolarining bir-biriga va guruhda sodir bo'layotgan voqealarga nisbatan sub'ektiv his-tuyg'ulari va his-tuyg'ularini ob'ektivlashtirish, og'zaki mulohaza yuritish, o'zaro erkinlik muhiti va muloqot erkinligi, ishtirokchilar, psixologik xavfsizlik muhiti. Ushbu xususiyatlar doirasida bir-biridan bir necha jihatdan farq qiluvchi o'ziga xos o'qitish shakllarining juda ko'p sonli modifikatsiyalari mavjud. Ushbu shakllardan biri kommunikativ kompetentsiyani (kommunikativ kompetentsiya, muloqot qobiliyatlari) rivojlantirish uchun treningdir. Kommunikativ kompetentsiyani o'qitish asoslari Andreeva G. A., Bogomolova N. N., Emelyanov Yu. N., Petrovskaya L. A., Xarash A. I. va boshqalarning ishlarida batafsil muhokama qilingan. Kommunikativ kompetentsiya tabiiy ravishda yuzaga kelmaydi, balki

maxsus texnikalar yordamida yuzaga keladi. maxsus ta'sir holatlarini yaratishdan iborat. Kommunikativ kompetentsiyani o'rgatish o'zaro bog'liqlik, o'zaro ifodalash, o'zaro tushunish, munosabatlar, o'zaro ta'sir jarayonlarini o'zlashtirish bilan bog'liq ijtimoiy-psixologik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishdan iborat. psixologik jihatdan to'g'ri va vaziyatga qarab muloqotga kirishish qobiliyati; aloqani saqlab qolish, sherikning faoliyatini psixologik rag'batlantirish qobiliyati; muloqotni yakunlash "nuqtasini" psixologik jihatdan aniq belgilash qobiliyati; o'z strategik yo'nalishini amalga oshirish uchun kommunikativ vaziyatning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlaridan maksimal darajada foydalanish qobiliyati; muloqot rivojlanayotgan kommunikativ vaziyatni rivojlantirishning mumkin bo'lgan usullarini bashorat qilish qobiliyati; sheriklarning o'zlarining kommunikativ harakatlariga munosabatini bashorat qilish qobiliyati; aloqa sheriklarining hissiy ohangiga psixologik moslashish qobiliyati, muloqotda tashabbusni qo'lga olish va ushlab turish qobiliyati; aloqa sherigining "istalgan reaksiyasini" qo'zg'atish qobiliyati; muloqotda sherikning ijtimoiy-psixologik kayfiyatini shakllantirish va "boshqarish" qobiliyati

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR;

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**EFFECT OF CHANGES IN MEAN ARTERIAL PRESSURE AND
INTRACRANIAL PRESSURE ON BRAIN PERFUSION IN PATIENTS WITH
TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY.**

Rakhimov A.P

Yunusov R.Kh.

*Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy
Urgench, Uzbekistan.*

The aim of the study was to assess the state of brain perfusion with changes in ICP (intracranial pressure) and MAP (mean arterial pressure) in patients with traumatic brain injury (TBI), and to determine their relationship.

Material and Methods: On the basis of the II TMA clinic in the ICU, we studied brain perfusion by choosing the optimal value of MAP and CPP (cerebral perfusion pressure) in (n=50) patients with TBI aged 18-55 years during the first decade after injury. Of these (n=5) women.

According to the outcome of traumatic brain injury, the patients were divided into two groups: I — main group (n=25) with concomitant TBI and II — control group (n=25) with isolated TBI. All patients were measured intracranial pressure by method of fiberoptic lumbar puncture at the level of L3-L4.

Cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) and MAP (mean arterial pressure) were calculated according to the generally accepted formula: $MAP = SBP + 2DBP / 3$, $CPP = MAP - ICP$. ICP and CPP were studied in the first decade after injury. Registration of their indicators was carried out simultaneously. The level of consciousness of the victims was assessed using the Glasgow Coma Scale.

Results and discussion: MAP was maintained at (70-100 mm Hg) with the help of vasopressors. With such an indicator of MAP, CPP was 60-80 mm Hg, which is an important level for ensuring normal blood flow to the brain. In order to adequately reduce ICP, mannitol and 10% hypertonic saline were used in standard doses.

The correlation between changes in MAP and CPP indicated that the magnitude of ICP was determined by the nature of cerebral damage, which was the leading and determining indicator in the diagnosis and treatment of primary brain damage. MAP was directly correlated with intracranial pressure, which indicated the possibility of indirectly assessing cerebral perfusion and impaired cerebral blood flow.

In assessing cerebral perfusion, changes in MAP and intracranial pressure (ICP) play an important role, since an increase in ICP occurs in 70% - 80% of cases in the acute period of traumatic brain injury and is the cause of high mortality and disability in patients.

Conclusion: Timely correction of MAP and adequate reduction of ICP during the first decade after injury is important in the prognosis of the disease.

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF BUPIVACAINE IN SMALL
DOSES IN SPINAL ANESTHESIA IN SURGICAL OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
PURULENT NECROTIC COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC FOOT.**

Rakhimov A.P

Yunusov R.Kh.

*Urgench branch of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. Urgench, Uzbekistan.*

Diabetes mellitus and its complications - Diabetic foot syndrome and purulent necrotic complication is the cause of disability and a decrease in the quality of life and leading to early death of patients. And it can develop within 5-15 years.

DFS (diabetic foot syndrome) and its purulent necrotic complication require periodic surgical treatment of the wound, and at the same time, in order to provide pain relief, the use of spinal anesthesia has its own characteristics when activating patients in the early postoperative period.

Purpose of the study: To evaluate the effectiveness of bupivacaine and compare the use of high doses (15 mg) and low doses (5 mg) for spinal anesthesia in surgical operations in patients with diabetic foot syndrome and its purulent-necrotic complications.

Materials and methods of research: We have studied on the basis of the TMA of the Urgench branch in the city hospital of the surgical department 120 sick women and men aged 35-80 years with diabetes mellitus and its purulent-necrotic complication in surgical operations using 0.5% hyperbaric solution in dose of 15 mg 3 ml (large dose) and 5 mg 1 ml (small dose) and analyzed the effectiveness results.

According to the 293rd law of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, patients were taken with an operational - anesthetic risk of class II-III-IV.

Patients are divided into 2 groups. Group 1 patients n=60 received a standard dose of 15 mg (3 ml) of bupivacaine hyperbaric solution and group 2 patients n=60 received a 5 mg (ml) dose of bupivacaine hyperbaric solution for spinal anesthesia in diabetic foot surgery. Spinal anesthesia was performed at the L3-L4 level and the patients were placed in a horizontal position. To compare and evaluate the effectiveness of anesthesia and analgesia at two different doses, cold tests were performed to determine the level of sensory block.

During anesthesia and surgery, hemodynamic parameters such as blood pressure, pulse, peripheral blood saturation and respiratory rate were monitored and observed.

Results of the study: In monitoring group 1, in many cases, the level of sensory block in Th6 was determined, and this required periodic use of vasopressors to maintain blood pressure at a normal level. In cases of high sensory block and when

the puls rate below 50 times per minute. 0.1% atropine was used and infusion therapy with crystalloids (15-20 ml/kg) was performed to optimize blood pressure.

In the second group, the spinal anesthesia performed differed from the first group with stable hemodynamics and early recovery in the postoperative period.

Observation parameters Group 1 (control) Group 2 (main)

Average blood pressure mm. Hg. 60 ± 5 96 ± 10

Pulse in 1 minute 50 > ± 5 60 ± 5

Blood Saturation 90% ± 2 94% ± 2

Sensor Unit Level Up to Th6 ±L5 До Th10 ± L5

Infusion therapy (crystalloids) 20 ± 30 ml/kg 10 ± 20 ml/kg

Activation of patients 240 ± 30 minutes 90 ± 30 minutes

Conclusion: It was found that the use of a hyperbaric solution of bupivacaine 0.5% in low doses of 5 mg (1 ml) for spinal anesthesia in surgical operations in patients with diabetic foot syndrome and its purulent necrotic complications is safe and effective.

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FUQAROLIK JAMIYATINING MILLATLARARO MUNOSABATLAR BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI

Toshpo'latov Mamadali Zayniddin o'g'li

Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti magistranti

Annotatsiya. Millatlararo munosabatlar masalasi har qanday demokratik davlat siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Bugungi globallashuv, o'zaro bog'liqlik millatlararo bag'rikenglik masalasini yanada nozik masala sifatida kun tartibiga qo'yimoqda. Millatlararo munosabatlarga noto'g'ri, bir tomonlama yondoshuv ko'plab salbiy oqibatlar, xattoki katta uruslarni ham keltirib chiqarganiga tarixdan ham, bugungi kundan ham ko'plab misollarni keltirish mumkin. Buning oldini olish uchun davlat siyosati tolerantlikka asoslanishi lozim. Mazkur maqolada tolerantlikka asoslangan davlat siyosatini amalga oshirishda fuqarolik jamiyati institutlarining roli, asosiy vazifalari o'rganilgan. Tegishli taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: fuqarolik jamiyati, fuqarolik jamiyati institutlari, millatlararo munosabatlar, tolerantlik, etnosiyosat, teng huquqlilik, o'zini o'zi boshqarish.

РОЛЬ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ МЕЖЭТНИЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ

Аннотация. Вопрос межэтнических отношений — одно из главных направлений любой демократической государственной политики. Сегодняшняя глобализация, взаимозависимость поднимают вопрос межэтнической терпимости как более чувствительный вопрос. В истории и сегодня есть много примеров того, что неправильный, односторонний подход к межэтническим отношениям привел к множеству негативных последствий, вплоть до крупных войн. Чтобы предотвратить это, государственная политика должна основываться на толерантности. В статье исследуются роль и основные задачи институтов гражданского общества в реализации государственной политики, основанной на толерантности. Разработаны соответствующие предложения и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: гражданское общество, институты гражданского общества, межэтнические отношения, толерантность, этнополитика, равенство, самоуправление.

THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF INTERETHNIC RELATIONS

Abstract. *The issue of interethnic relations is one of the main directions of any democratic state policy. Today's globalization, interdependence, raises the issue of interethnic tolerance as a more sensitive issue. There are many examples from history and today that the wrong, one-sided approach to interethnic relations has led to many negative consequences, even major wars. To prevent this, public policy must be based on tolerance. This article examines the role and main tasks of civil society institutions in the implementation of public policy based on tolerance. Relevant suggestions and recommendations have been developed.*

Keywords: *civil society, civil society institutions, interethnic relations, tolerance, ethnopolitics, equality, self-government.*

Fuqarolik jamiyatida har bir shaxs hamma vaqt ham davlat bilan bevosita munosabatlarga kirishmaydi. Fuqarolarning turli tuman uyushmalari, jamoalari mavjud bo'ladi, ular orqali fuqarolar o'z manfaatlarini, huquq va erkinliklarini muhofaza qiladilar, buzilgan huquqlarini tiklashda davlat idoralari bilan munosabatga kirishadilar. Ularning asoslari Konstitutsiyada, "Fuqarolik kodeksi", "Mehnat kodeksi", "Jamoat birlashmalari to'g'risida", "Fuqarolarning o'zini-o'zi boshqarish organlari to'g'risida", "Oliy Majlisning inson huquqlari bo'yicha vakili (Ombudsman) to'g'risida", "Fuqarolarning murojaatlari to'g'risida", "Davlat idoralari fuqarolar huquqlarini kamsituvchi g'ayriqonuniy xatti-harakatlari ustidan sudga shikoyat qilish tartibi to'g'risida" kabi qonunlarda belgilab berilgan. Fuqarolik jamiyatida davlat hokimiyati bilan fuqaro (fuqaroviy uyushmalar, guruhlar hamda jamoat birlashmalari) o'zaro teng, huquqiy (shuningdek, siyosiy-iqtisodiy) munosabatlarning erkin ishtirokchilari hisoblanadi. Bunday jamiyatning siyosiy asosini huquqiy davlat va unga bog'liq demokratik siyosiy tuzum, iqtisodiy zaminini esa xususiy mulkchilikka asoslangan bozor iqtisodiyoti tashkil qiladi. Konstitutsiyada fuqarolik jamiyatining muhim tarkibiy qismlari va institutlari bo'lmish oila, maktab, jamoat birlashmalari, siyosiy partiyalar, ommaviy axborot vositalari, fuqarolarning o'zini-o'zi boshqarish organlari (mahalla), diniy muassasalar, jamg'armalar, uyushma va ittifoqlar va boshqalarning huquqiy maqomi asoslari mustahkamlab qo'yilgan.(1) Jamoatchilik g'oyalari, xalq, elatlar manfaatlarini mahalla yaxshi biladi. Shu bois, jamiyatda barqarorlikni, totuvlikni, ijtimoiy adolatni ro'yobga chiqarishda mahallaning o'zni beqiyosdir. Mahalla hozir millatlararo munosabatlarni mustahkamlashning eng ta'sirchan instituti bo'lib bormoqda.(2) Bugun respublikamizda aholining barcha qatlamlarini birlashtirgan 62 ta jamiyat, 4 ta qo'mita, 32 assotsiatsiya, 21 ta tarmoq kasaba uyushmalari, 38 ta jamg'arma, 15 uyushma, 32 ta federatsiya, 1500 ta mahalliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan jamoat birlashmalari, 70 ta xorijiy mamlakatlarning jamoat va nohukumat tashkilotlari va ularning vakolatxonalari faoliyat ko'rsatmoqda.

Milliy-etnik jarayonlar jamiyatda kechayotgan islohotlardan, ijtimoiy munosabatlar va demokratik o'zgarishlardan alohida ro'y bermaydi, millatlararo munosabatlar umumijtimoiy voqelikning tarkibiy qismi sifatida ular bilan birga transformatsiyaga uchraydi, yangi shakl va mohiyat kasb etadi. Fuqarolik institutlari jamiyat rivojlanishining yo'nalishlarini belgilab berganidek, ularning o'zi ham ijtimoiy, shuningdek, millatlararo munosabatlarning mahsulidir. Ijtimoiy jarayonlar bilan milliy- etnik munosabatlar o'rtasidagi mazkur dialektik bog'liqlik hech qachon tekis, hamma etnoslarda aynan o'xshash kechmagan. Milliy-etnik jarayonlarni bunday sxematik, sodda tushunish murakkab milliy munosabatlar va ularning ijtimoiy jarayonlar bilan bog'liqligidagi o'ziga xoslikni, betakrorlikni chuqur anglashga, tadqiq etishga xohish yo'qligi yoki ilmiy metodologiyaning reallik oldidagi zaifligidir. Biroq etnopluralizm milliy-etnik jarayonlarni rasional tashkil etuvchi va boshqaruvchi sub'ektlar, markaz va yadrolar bo'lishi shartligini inkor qilmaydi. Etnopluralizm shunday sub'ektlarning e'tiboridan chekkada qolgan zahoti jamiyatda boshboshdoqlik, xaos, oxir natijada nizolar tug'iladi.(3) Shuning uchun ham fuqarolik jamiyatida amal qiladigan subyektlar - siyosiy partiyalar, nodavlat tashkilotlari, o'zini-o'zi boshqarish organlari huquqiy talablarga qat'iy rioya etishi shart. Aynan shu tarzda ular demokratik, huquqiy qadriyatlarini hayot tarziga aylantirishga hissa qo'shadilar. Bu borada juda ko'plab tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan. Ularning deyarli barchasida siyosiy-ijtimoiy institutlarning yetakchilik roli tan olinadi. Qonunlarga yangicha ruh bag'ishlash, me'yoriy hujjatlarni davr talabi asosida ko'rib chiqish, inson huquqlarini ta'minlash Oliy Majlis - milliy Parlament faoliyatida asosiy o'rin egallab kelmoqda. Qonunlarni ishlab chiqishda u asosiy e'tiborini inson huquqlariga qaratadi. Chunki qonun hamma uchun majburiy bo'lmog'i, davlat organlari, mansabdor shaxslar, jamoat birlashmalari va barcha fuqarolar qonunga asosan ish ko'rishlari talab etiladi. Shu bilan birga O'zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi Respublika hududida qonunlar bir xil qo'llanilishini, barcha fuqarolar qonun oldida tengligini kafolatlaydi. Bu haqda Konstitutsiyaning 18- moddasida shunday deyilgan: "O'zbekiston Respublikasida barcha fuqarolar bir xil huquq va erkinliklarga ega bo'lib, jinsi, irqi, millati, tili, dini, ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi, e'tiqodi, shaxsi va ijtimoiy mavqeidan qat'iy nazar, qonun oldida tengdir". (5) Fuqarolik jamiyatida amal qiladigan qonunlar uni, ya'ni fuqarolik jamiyatini huquqiy demokratik davlat bilan strategik maqsadi hamda funksional xususiyatlariga muvofiq yaqinlashtiradi. X.T.Odilqoriyev va Sh.U.Yakubov yozganidek: "huquqiy davlat fuqarolik jamiyatiga qarama-qarshi qo'yilmaydi. Ular bir-birining rivojlanishi uchun zaruriy shart-sharoitlar hisoblanadi". (6) Millatlararo munosabatlardagi o'zgarishlar ushbu "shart-sharoitlar" asosida yuz beradi va ularga internasional, gumanistik mohiyat baxsh etadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, bugungi kunda respublikamizda qo'lga kiritilgan millatlararo totuvlikni ta'minlashda imkoniyat yaratgan chora-tadbirlar milliy

o'zlikni qayta tiklash jarayonlari barqarorlikni ta'minlashda asosiy zamin bo'lgan huquqiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, madaniy va ma'naviy mexanizmlar haqida tahlillar fikr yuritish imkonini beradi. Aytish mumkinki, mamlakatimizda yashayotgan har bir fuqaro o'z milliy ravnaqi uchun intilishlari haq-huquqlari, ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun millatlararo munosabatlarning huquqiy asosi yaratildi. Bu fuqarolarning tengligini va erkinligini ta'minlaydi, shuningdek, fuqarolarga teng saylov huquqini berilishi barcha fuqarolarni irqi, millati, dini va boshqa belgilaridan qat'iy nazar, qonun oldida teng deb e'lon qilinishi tufayli ularni davlat va jamiyat hayotida faol ishtirok etishlari uchun keng yo'l ochadi. Mavjud qonunchiligimizdagi mazkur qoidalar xalqaro huquq normalariga to'la mos kelib, O'zbekiston qonunlarini demokratik ruhdaligini jahon amaliyotidagi ilg'or yutuqlarni o'ziga mujassam etganidan darak beradi.

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Toshpo'latov Mamadali Zayniddin o'g'li

Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti magistranti

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada Fuqarolik jamiyati tushinchasining kelib chiqishi, uni qanday mezonlar asosida qurish mumkinligi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada fuqarolik jamiyatini barpo etishda milliy qadriyatlarning o'rniga alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Fuqarolik jamiyati, qonun, "Avesto", "Fozil odamlar shahri", qadriyat, ozodlik, tinchlik, demokratiya.*

СОЗДАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА-ТРЕБОВАНИЕ ЭПОХИ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются истоки понятия гражданское общество, по каким критериям оно может быть построено. Также в статье особое внимание уделяется роли национальных ценностей в построении гражданского общества.*

Ключевое слова: *гражданское общество, закон, "Авеста", "Город добродетельных людей", ценность, свобода, мир, демократия.*

CREATION OF A MODERN CIVIL SOCIETY-THE DEMAND OF THE ERA

Abstract. *The article reflects on the origin of civil society dream, on what criteria it can be built on. The article also specifically addresses the place of national values in the establishment of civil society.*

Keywords: *civil society, law, "Avesto", "City of friendly people", value, freedom, peace, democracy.*

Fuqarolik jamiyati - konstitutsiyaviy huquq nazariyasida huquq va demokratiyaga asoslangan ijtimoiy hayotning zarur oqilona usuli; insonga uning iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy hayoti shakllarini erkin tanlash kafolatlanadigan, qonun ustuvorligi va inson huquqlari hamda erkinliklari qaror topadigan, ko'p partiyaviylik, siyosiy institutlar, mafkura va fikrlarning xilma-xilligi ta'minlanadigan hamda o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlarining mavqei baland bo'lgan ijtimoiy tuzum. [1] Bunda mamlakatning har bir fuqarosi siyosiy, ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, ma'naviy va huquqiy jihatdan o'z ehtiyojlarini jamoat birlashmalari va fondlari, o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlari, siyosiy partiyalar va nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar ishida faol ishtirok etib, ular orqali qondiradilar.

Fuqarolik jamiyatida fuqarolar davlat faoliyati ustidan jamoatchilik nazoratini o'rnatadilar, davlatning ko'pgina vakolatlari jamoat tashkilotlari zimmasiga yuklanadi. Davlat hokimiyati esa mamlakatning umumiy taraqqiyot rejalarini tuzadi, uning strategiyasini ishlab chiqadi, mudofaa, milliy xavfsizlik, davlat mustaqilligi va chegaralari daxlsizligini, uning suverenitetini ta'minlash, pul-moliya, soliq, bank siyosati, tashqi siyosat va jahon hamjamiyati bilan aloqalar tizimini yaratadi, uni boshqaradi. Fuqarolik jamiyatini qurish kuchli davlatdan kuchli jamiyat sari bosqichma bosqich o'tish orqali ro'y beradi.

Fuqarolik jamiyati haqida ilk tasavvurlar Aristotelning "Siyosat" asarida bayon etilgan.[2] Unga ko'ra, insonning erkin yashash huquqi kishilik jamiyatining adolat va qonun ustuvorligi asosida tashkil etilishi orqali ta'minlanishi lozim. Jamiyatni boshqarishda qonunlarning to'g'ri va adolatli bo'lishiga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Bu g'oyalar XVII asrga kelib keng rivojlandi.

Jumladan, T.Gobbs asarlarida takomillashtiriddi. XVIII asr Buyuk fransuz inqilobi davrida Inson va fuqaro huquqlari deklaratsiyasi e'lon qilinishi bilan esa fuqarolik jamiyati tushunchasi keng tarqala boshladi. Chunki jamiyatning teng huquqli a'zolari — "fuqarolar" tushunchasi paydo bo'ldi, ular jamiyat va davlat manfaatlarini bilan bog'langan shaxsiy manfaatlarini anglay boshladilar.

Sharqda Fuqarolik jamiyatining o'ziga xos talqini mavjud. Bu, bevosita, axloq, madaniyat va ma'naviyatning huquq bilan uyg'unlashgan, fe'l atvor, xatti harakatlar va qoida me'yorlarning uzviy uyg'unlashgan shakli bilan bog'liq. Jumladan, eng qadimiy madaniy tarixiy huquqiy yodgorlik — Avestoda kishilarning uyushib yashashi, o'zaro munosabatlar va aloqalarning axloq va me'yorlarga tayanishi kabi g'oyalar ilgari surilgan. Bunda o'z o'zidan jamiyatda qonun ustuvorligiga erishish, jamiyatni shaxs tomonidan emas, qonun boshqarishi kabi fuqarolik jamiyatining ilk belgilari namoyon bo'lgan. Forobiyning "Fozil odamlar shahri" asarida mamlakatni boshqarishda adolatli qonun zarurligi, faol fuqarolik jamiyatini shakllantirish mohiyati chuqur tahlil etilgan.[3] Qonunlari mukammal bo'lgan mamlakatda adolat, inson huquqlari ustuvor bo'lishi muqarrar ekanligi bayon qilib berilgan. Forobiyning fikriga ko'ra, "Shahar (mamlakat) aholisi xush xulqqa ega bo'lmagan taqdirda hokimiyatga ehtiyoj tug'iladi"[4], jinoyatchilik, bezorilik, qonunbuzarlik qonunlar zaif, aholi axloqiy ma'naviy jihatdan barkamol bo'lmagan sharoitda avj oladi.

O'zbekistonda fuqarolik jamiyatini qurish tarixiy an'ana bo'lsada, u butunlay yangi tarixiy sharoitlarda jahon davlatchiligi ilg'or tajribalari va ko'p ming yillik milliy an'analarning sintezi sifatida dunyoga kelmoqda. Ya'ni erkinlik va axloq, ozodlik va tarbiya, qonunga itoatkorlik va siyosiy huquqiy faollik, hurriyat va qat'iy tartib-intizom uyg'unligida fuqarolik jamiyati shakllantirilmoqda.

Bunday fikr bildirishimizga muayyan tarixiy sharoitlarda obyektiv zaruratlar tufayli jamiyat rivojlanishi uchun milliy qadriyatlar diniy qarashlar bag'rida

shakllanganligidir. Shunga ko'ra bizning milliy qadriyatlarimiz faqat islom zaminida vujudga kelmagan, balki zardushtiylik, buddaviylik kabi dinlardan ham ko'p narsalarni olgan. Binobarin, har qanday qadriyatlarning bosh manbai ijtimoiy hayotdir.

Uning zaruratini birinchi Prezidentimiz I.A.Karimov alohida va bir necha marta ta'kidlab kelgan. "Mustaqillik yillarida eng katta qo'lga kiritgan yutuqlarimizdan biri tarixiy, milliy va axloqiy qadriyat hamda an'analarning, muqaddas dinimizning jamiyatni ma'naviy yuksalishidagi o'rni va ahamiyatini qayta tiklanganligidir. Ayni zamonda, tajovuzkor aqidaparast kuchlar islom dini xalqimiz uchun muqaddas qadriyat ekanligidan foydalanib, O'zbekistonni demokratik, ma'rifiy taraqqiyot yo'lidan og'dirishga intilmoqdalar". [5] Keyingi yillarda dunyo miqyosida islomdan qarama-qarshi maqsad yo'lida foydalanishlar yaqqol namoyon bo'lmoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, insoniyatning eng umumiy jamoasi bo'lgan jamiyatgina, umuminsoniy qadriyatlarning yaratguvchisi va saqlab turuvchisidir. Umuminsoniy qadriyatlar nihoyatda keng ko'lami va serqirra tushuncha. Uning zaminida eng avvalo ozodlik, erkinlik, tinchlik, demokratiya tufayli shakllangan inson baxt-saodati kabi umumijtimoiy mahno va mazmun kashf etadigan qadriyatlardan iborat, deyish mumkin. Qadriyatlarni faqat moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar sifatida tushunish va uni shunday izohlash ham ilmiy nuqtai nazardan to'g'ri emas.

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STEAM TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF
O'QUVCHILARINING TANQIDIY-TAHLILIIY HAMDA KREATIV
FIKRLASHLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Xodiyeva Gulhayo Hasan qizi

mustaqil tadqiqotchi.

gxodiyeva@inbox.ru

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativ hamda mantiqiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish masalalari: boshlang'ich sinf darslarida integrativ yondashuvdan samarali foydalanish, Steam ta'lim texnologiyasi va uning ahamiyati, didaktik o'yinlar vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining turli qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasi, kreativ fikrlash, tanqidiy-tahliliy tafakkur, zamonaviy kasblar, integrativ yondashuv, zamonaviy metodlar, didaktik o'yinlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье будут обсуждаться вопросы развития творческого и логического мышления учащихся младших классов: эффективное использование интегративного подхода на занятиях начальной школы, образовательная технология Steam и ее значение, развитие различных способностей учащихся младших классов посредством дидактических игр.

Ключевые слова. Образовательные технологии STEAM, креативное мышление, критико-аналитическое мышление, современные профессии, интегративный подход, современные методы, дидактические игры.

Abstract: In this article, the issues of developing creative and logical thinking of elementary school students, effective use of an integrative approach in elementary school classes, Steam educational technology and its importance, development of various abilities of elementary school students through didactic games will be discussed.

Keywords: STEAM educational technology, creative thinking, critical-analytical thinking, modern professions, integrative approach, modern methods, educational games.

Kirish. Jahon ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha o'tkazilgan Xalqaro ta'lim forumida 2030-yilga qadar tasdiqlangan barqaror ta'lim konsepsiyasida ta'lim taraqqiyotning asosiy harakatlantiruvchi kuchi va barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga yetkazuvchi muhim faoliyatli sifatida e'tirof etilib, bu borada umumta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarni mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, yangi avlod darsliklari va zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari amaliyotga tadbiq etilmoqda, integrativ yondashuv asosida mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish, boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarida mustaqil ta'lim olish faoliyatini rivojlantirish, o'quv-metodik ta'minotini yaratish bo'yicha loyihalarni amaliyotga tadbiq etishga

doir tizimli ishlar olib borilmoqda. Jahon ta'lim va ilmiy tadqiqot muassasalarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy mushohada qilish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning kreativ mexanizmlari ta'lim jarayoniga tadbiiq etish ta'limning nazariy-metodologik jihatlarini takomillashtirish, umumta'lim maktablarining boshlang'ich sinflarida ta'limni zamonaviy talablar asosida tashkil etish va mazmunan yangilash, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining fan va ishlab chiqarish bilan integratsiyalashuvi bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda, o'quvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda yo'naltirilgan o'quv vaziyatlarining didaktik-pedagogik imkoniyatlari va texnologiyalarini aniqlashtirish boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlash jarayonini takomillashtirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

STEAM texnologiyasi ta'limdan farqli ravishda bilimlarni alohida emas, o'zaro mutanosib holda integrativ tarzda olib borishni ta'minlab beradi. O'quvchi o'zida nostandart fikrlash, muammoga bir nechta yechim topish va ijodkorlik ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi va bu uning kelajakdagi faoliyatida juda qo'l keladi.

STEAM ta'limi o'sib borayotgan ta'lim fanlari tarmog'ini, biznes va jamiyatni bog'lash uchun foydalaniladigan asosni ta'minlaydi, bunda fuqarolar ishtirok etadigan, global ma'suliyatli, yoqelikka asoslangan dasturlarni yaratish mumkin. Ushbu yondoshuv samarasi o'laroq olingan bilim o'z tajribalari va ta'lim, ixtiro, tadbirkorlik va hayotga ta'siri haqida yangi va chuqurroq yo'llar bilan o'ylashga majbur qiladi. Steam ta'limi o'zi nimani anglatadi? Ushbu savolga javob quyidagicha: ta'limni integratsiyalashgan holda olib borish yani barcha sohalarni ta'lim, fan va texnologiyani va ishlab chiqarish, biznes sohalari aloqasini etirof etgan holda, muhokama va tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradigan tizimdir. Jahondagi ta'lim bo'yicha ekspertlarning ta'kidlashicha, STEAM ta'limi o'quvchilarda quyidagi qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

- O'ylab tavakkal qilish;
- Mazmunli o'quv faoliyati bilan shug'ullanish;
- Bardoshli muammolarni hal qiluvchilarga aylanish;
- Hamkorlikda ishlash;
- Ijodiy jarayon orqali ishlash;

Shu bilan birgalikda STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasida tanqidiy-tahliliy hamda kreativ fikrlash alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bugungi globallashuv zamonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativ hamda tanqidiy-tahliliy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish dolzarb masaladir. Zero, jahon statistikasida kelajak kasblarining katta qismi aynan STEAM mutaxassislari bo'lishi alohida ta'kidlab o'tilgan, bu esa o'quvchilarning kichik yoshidan boshlab STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasi hamda ularning turli kasblarga bo'lgan layoqatlarini esa boshlang'ich sinfdanoq rivojlantirish zarurligini anglatadi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. Bugungi kunda dunyo ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish, ularda mantiqiy, tanqidiy va kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirishning didaktik tizimini takomillashtirishga doir qator ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Ayniqsa, fanlararo integrativ mazmunini takomillashtirish, o'quvchilarda o'zini o'zi rivojlantirish tayanch kompetentsiyasini shakllantirish orqali intellektual-madaniy rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik mexanizmlarini samarali yo'lga qo'yish orqali o'quvchilarda ilmiy dunyoqarashni fanlararo shakllantirishning didaktik ta'minotini takomillashtirishdan iborat.

XXI asrda jahon miqyosida ta'limga barqaror taraqqiyotini ta'minlovchi asosiy omil sifatida e'tirof etilib, 2030-yilgacha belgilangan Xalqaro ta'lim konsepsiyasida sifatli ta'lim olish va ijodiy qobiliyatni rag'batlantirish dolzarb vazifa sifatida belgilandi. Ta'limni globallashtirish va integratsiyalashuv jarayonlariga moslashtirishda rivojlangan mamlakatlar ta'lim tizimida o'quvchi yoshlarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishning mobil va ta'sirchan modellarini ishlab chiqish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu esa ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarning ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirish va o'quv materiallarini fanlararo aloqadorlik tamoyillari asosida egallashda kasbiy kompetentlikni o'rtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mamlakatimizda ta'lim-tarbiya tizimini isloh qilish, ilmiy kadrlar tayyorlashni zamon talablari darajasiga ko'tarish, iqtidorli yoshlarning ilmiy dunyo qarashini shakllantirishda integratsiyalashgan ta'limni keng qamrovda yo'lga qo'yish sohasida keng ko'lamlı chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida ta'lim va fan sohasida innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirish, xususan, mehnat bozorining zamonaviy ehtiyojlarini inobatga olgan holda, malakali kadrlar tayyorlash siyosatini tizimli amalga oshirish ustuvor vazifa sifatida belgilanib, ta'limning bosh bo'g'oyasi, bu fan va uning doimiy rivojlanishidir. Respublikamizda ilmiy ijod erkinligi, ilmiy-tadqiqotchilik faoliyati bilan shug'ullanish, o'quvchi yoshlarda ilmiy dunyo qarashni shakllantirish va qo'llab quvvatlash borasida bir qator me'yoriy hujjatlarni ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Mamlakatimiz ilmiy tadqiqotchilaridan: N.A.Ataqulova, A.Risboyev, Sh.Jo'rayev, A.Tashatov, P.I.Ivanov, M.Y.Zufarova, F.I.Ochilov, M.Asqarova, M.Xayitboyev, M.S.Nishonov, Z.T.Nishonova, G.N.Najmiddinova, A.K.Raximov, Sh.Sharipov va boshqalar o'quvchi yoshlarda ilmiy dunyoqarashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini o'rgangan bo'lsalar, A.Ch.Choriyev, N.S.Fayzullayeva, M.K.Ashirova, I.D.Zverev, R.A.Mavlonova, B.S.Abdullayeva, N.M.Ahmedova, N.X.Adilov, X.B.Norbo'tayev, N.J.Isakulova, M.B.Rahimqulova, M.Rahmatullayeva N.M.Saloxitdinova, H.T.Omonov, A.A.Xasanov va boshqalar fanlararo aloqadorlikning tarkibiy qismi, darajalari, integrativ ta'lim tizimi samaradorligi haqida izlanishlar olib borganlar.

MDH davlatlari olimlaridan: N.S.Svetlovskaya, L.N.Baxareva, A.N.Leontev, L.T.Tarasov, N.F.Dobrynin, V.V.Davydov, N.B.Istomina, I.YA.Kaplunovich,

T.N.Sherbakova, A.N. Kolmogorovlar o'quvchilar tafakkuri va ularning ilmiy dunyoqarashini takomillashtirishga doir ilmiy izlanishlar olib borgan bo'lsalar,

M.N.Berulava, V.A.Lazareva, YU.M.Kolyagin, O.J.Alekseenko, A.YA.Danilyuk, YU.A.Kustov, I.P.Rachenko, M.A.Rozova, N.K.Chapayev, M.N.Skatkin kabi olimlar ta'limda fanlar integratsiyasi muammolari o'rganganlar.

Rivojlangan xorijiy davlatlarda ilmiy dunyo qarash va fanlar integratsiyasi bo'yicha O.Behling, S.K.Reed, K.H.Silber, P.D.Mitchell, R.J.Sternberg, Kel Nyuport, L.Masterman, A.Hart, S.Hennessy, K.Ruthvenlar tomonidan amalga oshirilgan. STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasi ham matematika, texnologiya, injenerlik, san'at va dizayn kabi fan va sohalarning integratsiyasidan tashkil topgan ta'lim texnologiyasidir.

Respublikamizda so'ngi yillarda integrativ yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy va aqliy faoliyatining imkoniyatlarini o'rganish, boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarida mantiqiy mushohada qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish, o'quv jarayonini integrativ yondashuv asosida mazmunli tashkillashtirishning me'yoriy asoslari yaratilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoyevning "Yoshlarimiz mustaqil fikrlaydigan, yuksak intellektual va ma'naviy salohiyatga ega bo'lib, dunyo miqyosida o'z tengdoshlariga hech qaysi sohada bo'sh kelmaydigan insonlar bo'lib kamol topishi, baxtli bo'lishi uchun davlatimiz va jamiyatimizning bor kuch va imkoniyatlarini safarbar etamiz."

-degan da'vatlari ta'limning sifatli va samarali tashkil etilishini, ayniqsa, boshlang'ich sinflardan boshlab o'quvchilarni mustaqil fikrlaydigan, yuksak intellektual va ma'naviy salohiyatga ega shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida mantiqiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish bugungi kunda ta'lim tizimida hamda jamiyatimiz taraqqiyotida alohida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Xulosa. Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'quvchilar ilmiy dunyoqarashini fanlararo STEAM texnologiyasi asosida shu bilan birgalikda o'quvchilarni kasbiy qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish bugungi kunda ta'lim jarayonining ustuvor maqsadlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu jarayon taqdim etilgan nazariy bilim, amaliy ko'nikma, malaka va kompetensiyalarni o'quvchilar tomonidan sifatli hamda samarali o'zlashtirilishi, o'quv jarayonining yaxlit maqsadga yo'naltirilgan didaktik hodisa sifatida namoyon bo'lishi, boshlang'ich sinflarda tabiiy fanlarni matematika bilan fanlararo bog'lab o'qitishda o'quvchilar ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishga imkon beradi. O'quvchilarni intellektual rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim jarayonining samaradorligini ta'minlashda o'quv topshiriqlari va didaktik o'yinlar muhim pedagogik ahamiyatga ega. Boshlang'ich sinflarda tabiiy fanlarni matematika bilan fanlararo bog'lab o'qitishda o'quvchilar ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishda intellektual faoliyat ko'rsatishlari va o'z faoliyati natijalarini baholashga alohida e'tibor qaratilishi lozim. Bu kabi usullar o'quvchilarning kreativ hamda tanqidiy-tahliliy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirishga, ularning o'z ustilarida ishlash ko'nikmalarini

shakllantirishlarizga yaqindan yordam beradi, didaktik o'yinlar esa o'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlashlarini rivojlantirishga va muammolarni yechishga o'rgatadi.

Didaktik o'yinlarni ikki guruhga bo'lish mumkin: vizual va og'zaki. Ko'rgazmali qurollardan foydalanadigan o'yinlar, o'z navbatida, namoyish va tarqatma materiallar bilan o'yinlarga va turli o'yinchoqlar (tabiat buyumlari va uy-ro'zg'or buyumlari) bilan o'yinlarga bo'linadi. So'z o'yinlari bolalarning to'plangan tajribasiga, ularni kuzatishga asoslangan. Ushbu o'yinlarning vazifasi tizimlashtirish va umumlashtirishdir. Ular o'quv materialini mustahkamlash va takrorlash bosqichida qo'llaniladi. Og'zaki didaktik o'yinlar o'quv muammosini hal qilish jarayoni aqliy rejada, g'oyalar asosida va vizualizatsiyaga tayanmasdan amalga oshirilishi bilan ajralib turadi. Mos ravishda so'z o'yinlarini 4 guruhga bo'lish mumkin.

Ulardan birinchisi o'yinlarni o'z ichiga oladi, ularning yordamida obyektlar, hodisalarning muhim (asosiy) belgilarini ajratib ko'rsatish qobiliyati shakllanadi: "Taxmin", "Radio", "Qayerda edingiz?". Ikkinchi guruh bolalarda rivojlanish uchun ishlatiladigan o'yinlardan iborat. Taqqoslash, farqlash, to'g'ri xulosalar chiqarish qobiliyati: "Bu o'xshamaydi", "Kim ko'proq ertaklarni biladi". Obektlarni turli mezonlarga ko'ra umumlashtirish va tasniflash qobiliyati rivojlangan o'yinlar uchinchi guruh o'yinlariga birlashtiriladi: "Kimga nima kerak?", "Uchta obektni nomlang", "Bir so'z bilan nomlang". Maxsus, to'rtinchi guruhda diqqat, aql, tez fikrlash, chidamlilik, hazil tuyg'usini rivojlantirish uchun o'yinlar mavjud: "Buzilgan telefon", "Bo'yoqlar", "Chivinlar - uchmaydi", "Oq va qora, nomini ayt mang".

Didaktik o'yinlarning mazmuni o'quvchilarda ijtimoiy hayot hodisalari, tabiat va atrofdagi dunyo obektlariga to'g'ri munosabatni shakllantiradi. O'qituvchi didaktik o'yinlar yordamida bolalarni mustaqil fikrlashga, har xil sharoitda olgan bilimlaridan vazifaga muvofiq foydalanishga o'rgatadi. Ko'pgina didaktik o'yinlar bolalarni aqliy harakatlarda mavjud bo'lgan bilimlardan oqilona foydalanishga chorlaydi: atrofdagi narsalar va hodisalarda xarakterli xususiyatlarni topish; solishtirish, guruhlash, obektlarni ma'lum mezonlarga ko'ra tasniflash, to'g'ri xulosalar, umumlashtirishlar. Didaktik o'yinlarda namoyon bo'ladigan bolalarning fikrlash faoliyati mustahkam, chuqur bilimlarni egallashga ongli munosabatning asosiy shartidir.

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Zakhidov Mukhtar Makhmudovich

*T.N.Q. Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after
Niyaziy*

Alisher Navoi reveals in his papers the meaning of Hadith, and the mysticism in it, along with the artistic expression of Islamic-Iranian philosophy, also recognizes them as a source of development of noble qualities and positive characteristics. And tabarruk hadiths, once again, proves that the content embodied in him serves goodness, the perfection of the spiritual and spiritual world of man. Another aim was to make many people enjoy Muslim guidance, traditions and values, manners, qualities and qualities with expressed Hadith, as well as to enjoy the Turkic peoples of this beautiful creation.

M. The twenty –first gift of the system of “Arba’in”s of Jami, Navoi, Fuzuli in the Pulatova monograph is “inexhaustible wealth” [Imam Muhammad 2005: 195], it is said. The Lord of this hadith concludes the commentary as follows:

Jomiy:

sohibi hirsro zi xoni karam,
fayzi ehson namirasad hargiz.
Ba qanoat Garoy, kon ganjist,
Ki bapoyon namirasad hargiz.

Navoiy:

hirsdan kechkim, ul g'amedurkim,
haddu g'oyatemas anga paydo
Tut qanoatkim, ul erur mofe,
Ki, nihoyat anga emas paydo.

Fuzuliy:

Mali dunyaya meyil qilma kim,
ul, qobili naqs o'lan bezaetdir.
Odamizadaya tukenmez mal,

naqdi ganjinayi qanoatdir [Imom Muhammad 2005: 195].

In the "Arba'in", the pen of these three teacher poets, Hadith are written first in Arabic orthography and then in Persian and Turkic orthography. But in all three there is a call to man that being patient is the owner of inexhaustible wealth. There is a call to put ambition in its place to the fleeting riches, to have in its path a real wealth of various evils, betrayal of the right of men, not to oppress men, to have beautiful manners, human qualities and patience.

All three poets follow the path of applying an independent mode of expression, relying on their own opinion, without repeating each other. The result is a sample of

three independent beautiful works. When all three works are analyzed in religious and secular terms, of course, a person is harmonized with positive qualities, with the science of decency. In these aspects, the "Arba'in" are the "bouquet of adab", which confirms our opinion.

In the 15th century, Alisher Navoi made a worthy contribution to the science of literature-literature with many of his works. All his works have been serving the development of the spirituality of Turkic peoples for six centuries. Although the "Arba'in" were a small part of the work of the poet's Highness, by his own admission he was extremely pious, a feature deeply embedded in the composition of all his works. These views are expressed by the author M. Polachova was also reflected in her views.

In the fourteenth of the "Arba'in" created by the master poets, it is said: "Heaven is under the feet of mothers". This hadith continents are finished like this:

Jomiy:

Sar Ze modar makashki toji sharaf,
gard az rohi modaron boshad
Nok shav ziri poyi u ki bibisht,
dar qadamhoi modaron boshad.

Navoiy:

onalarning oyog'i ostidadur,
Ravzai jannatu jinon bog'i.
Ravza bog'in visolin istar ersang,
bo'lonaning oyog'i tufrog'i.

Fuzuliy:

analar ho'rmatin dutunki,
mudam, Gabili rahmati ilah o'lasiz.
Istek anlar ayag'i altinda,
gar dilarsizni, jannati o'lasiz [Imom Muhammad 2005: 190].

On these continents, all three poets express incredibly beautiful expressions. Talent and skill of all three poets are evident in their works. It is no secret to any of us that Paradise is under the feet of mothers in the centuries already. However, the irony of the word poets, the interpretation of their thought, the promotion of the most necessary moral idea, the importance of the work in the upbringing of children, while increasing the influence of Hadith, will become the basis for the creation of three independent works. In its place, it harmonizes our secular and religious teachings and expresses the continuity of the Quran and Hadith and fiction.

**ТУПРОҚҚА ИШЛОВ БЕРИШДАГИ АСОСИЙ АГРОТЕХНИК
ТАЛАБЛАР, ТУПРОҚНИНГ ЕЙИЛТИРУВЧИ ХОССАЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИ
ИШ ОРГАНЛАРИНИНГ РЕСУРСИГА ТАЪСИРИ**

Косимова Малоҳатхон Каримовна

Андижон машинасозлик институти доценти, т.ф.ф.д. (PhD)

Абдуллаев Шавкат Азимович

*ТМЖ кафедраси катта ўқитувчиси
Андижон машинасозлик институти*

Тупроқ яхлит бир масса эмас, балки уч фазали дисперс муҳит бўлиб, майдаланган ва ўзаро аралаштирилган қаттиқ, суюқ ҳамда газсимон заррачалардан иборат. Бундан ташқари, тупроқда ўсимлик қолдиқлари (илдизлар ва ўсимликлар пояси) ва тирик организмлар мавжуд. Микроорганизмлар органик қолдиқларни парчалаб, ўсимликларни минераллар билан озиклантирибгина қолмай, балки шу билан бирга тупроқ ҳосил қилиш жараёнида ҳам қатнашиб, унинг технологик хоссаларига ижобий таъсир кўрсатадиган гумусни қўпайишига ёрдам беради. Структурали тупроқда қаттиқ зарралар капилляр бўшликли агрегатларга (кесакчаларга) бирлашган. Кесакчалар орасида капилляр бўлмаган йирик ораликлар (гравитацион бўшлиқлар) мавжуд. Қаттиқ зарралар ораликлари сув ва ҳаво билан тўлганлиги туфайли, тупроқда қанча сув кўп бўлса шунча ҳаво кам бўлади ва аксинча. Тупроқнинг технологик хоссалари юқори даражада ундаги суюқ ва газсимон фазаларнинг нисбатига боғлиқ. Ушбу фазаларнинг оптимал нисбатини таъминлаш учун тупроққа механик ишлов берилади. Тупроқда унга экиладиган ўсимликларни эркин ўсиши, ривожланиши ва юқори ҳосил бериши учун унинг ҳолати энг қулай бўлиши керак. Ўсимликлар учун қулай шароит яратиш учун тупроққа ишлов беришнинг агротехник талаблари ишлаб чиқилади.

Агротехник талаблар. Шудгорлаш тупроққа ишлов беришнинг энг муҳим усули. Тупроқ қанча сифатли шудгорланса, ўсимлик уруғлари шунча яхши униб чиқади ва ривожланади, ҳосил юқори бўлади, бошқа қуроллар билан қўшимча ишлов бериш кам талаб қилинади.

Юқори сифатли шудгорга эришиш учун унга қўйиладиган қуйидаги агротехник талабларни бажариш керак:

- шудгор чуқурлиги белгиланган ҳайдаш чуқурлигига мос келиши керак, ўртача ҳайдаш чуқурлигидан йўл қўйилиши мумкин бўлган четлашишлар текис далаларда ± 1 см, нотекис рельефли далаларда ± 2 см дан ошмаслиги лозим;
- плугнинг хақиқий қамраш кенлиги унинг конструктив қамраш кенлигидан четлашиши ± 10 % гача рухсат этилади;
- тупроқ палаҳсаси тўлиқ ағдарилиши ва ўсимлик қолдиқлари, бегона ўт уруғлари, ўғитлар тўла ва чуқур қўмилиши керак;

- шудгор юзасидаги марзаларнинг баландлиги ва эгатларнинг чуқурлиги бўйича нотекислиги 5...7 см гача рухсат этилади;
- мақбул намликли далаларни шудгорлаганда 10 см дан катта кесакларнинг миқдори 15...20 % дан ошмаслиги керак;
- шудгорланган дала юзаси текис ва туташ бўлиши, чала ҳамда ҳайдалмаган ерлар бўлмаслиги керак;
- плуг корпуслари кесган палахсалар бир хил ўлчамда бўлиши керак;
- плугни қўшни ўтишлар орасида узилишлар ҳамда очик ва яширинча чала қолган ерлар, бутун пайкалда ҳамда эгатга киришда ва чиқишда шудгорланмаган қийиқларга рухсат этилмайди;
- марзалар остидаги шудгор чуқурлиги белгиланган ишлов чуқурлигининг ярмидан кичик, уларнинг баландлиги эса 7 см дан катта бўлмаслиги керак;
- шудгорлашдан ҳосил бўлган эгат тўғри чизикли бўлиши керак;
- шудгорлашда ҳосил бўладиган палахсалар майдаланиши ва тупроқ қатлами юмшатишга бўлиши лозим;
- шудгорланган даланинг четидаги бурилиш йўлакчалари шудгор қилиниши ва очик эгатлар текисланиши керак.

Ҳар йили экин экиладиган ерларни кузги шудгорлашда ҳамда қўриқ ерларни бирламчи шудгорлашда чимқирқар (ёки бурчакқирқар) билан жиҳозланган плугдан фойдаланиш мақсадга мувофиқдир. Шудгорланган ерни такрорий ҳайдашда ҳамда сочилган гўнгни кўмишда чимқирқарсиз плуг ишлатилади. Серилдиз жойларда палахсани ағдариб, кесакларни майдалашга интильмасдан шудгорлаш керак (кесаклар бошқа қуроллар ёрдамида кейинчалик майдаланади). Сертош ерлар сақлагичли плуг билан ҳайдалади.

Ерларни шудгорлашда унинг чуқурлигига алоҳида эътибор берилади. Шудгорлаш чуқурлиги тупроқ-иқлим шароитига, тупроқнинг унумдорлигига, ер юзасининг тупроқли қатламини чуқурлигига, механик таркибига, бегона ўтларнинг тарқалиш даражасига ҳамда алмашлаб экишнинг қайси даласи эканлигига қараб табақалаштирилган ҳолда белгиланади. Тупроқ энг қулай намликка (16-18 %) эга бўлган агротехник муддатларда, камида 20 см (маккажўхори ва пахта учун камида 30 см) чуқурликда шудгорланиши лозим. Андижон вилоятининг тоғ олди бўз тупроқларида (Андижон, Жалақудуқ, Қўрғонтепа, Хўжаобод, Пахтаобод, Булоқбоши туманлари) кузги шудгор 30 см, ҳайдалма қатлами қалин оч тусли бўз тупроқлар (Олтинқўл, Балиқчи, Марҳамат, Шаҳрихон, Пахтаобод, Избоскан, Бўз, Асака, Хўжаобод, Булоқбоши туманлари) 35-40 см чуқурликда ағдариб ҳайдалади. Устки қисми ярим метр чуқурликда гипс қатлами бўлган шўрланган тупроқларда (Улуғнор, Бўз туманлари) ва зич ҳайдов ости қаватли барча оғир тупроқли ерларда 50-60 см чуқурликда юмшатилиб, 28-30 см устки қатлами ағдариб ҳайдалади.

Тупроққа юқорида келтирилган агротехник талабларга жавоб берадиган сифатда ишлов берилиши тупроққа ишлов берадиган ясси иш органларининг

конструктив тузилишига ва физик-механик хоссаларига боғлиқ бўлади. Чунки улар тупроқнинг ҳаракатига қаршилиги билан ифодаланувчи оғир шароитларда ишлайди ва ишқаланиш натижасида тез ейилиб ишга яроқсиз ҳолга келади. Шунинг учун ҳам тупроққа ишлов берадиган машиналар иш органларининг ресурси бошқа ташкил этувчи деталларнинг ресурсига қараганда анча кам бўлиб қолмоқда ва улар ушбу машиналардан фойдаланиш самарадорлигига салбий таъсир кўрсатмоқда.

Бундан тупроққа ишлов берадиган машиналар иш органларнинг ейилиш тезлигини камайтирадиган ва натижада ресурсини оширадиган ҳар қандай илмий ва амалий тадқиқотлар натижалари қатта аҳамият касб этади деган хулоса келиб чиқади.

Шунинг учун ҳам, бугунги кунга қадар, ясси юзали иш органларининг ейилиш механизмини ўрганиш устида дунё олимлари томонидан қатор тадқиқотлар олиб борилган.

Олиб борилган тадқиқотларда аниқланганки, тупроққа ишлов берадиган машиналар ишчи органларининг хусусан лемехлар, папжалар, исканалар, наральниклар ва бошқаларнинг, асосий ейилиш тури бўлиб абразив ейилиш ҳисобланади. Ишчи органларнинг ейилиш муаммосини ечишда Фляйшер Ж., Мак-Грегори С.В., Байер Р.Ж., Полцер Г., Пурше Г., Кимура У., Гаркунов Д.Н., Чичинадзе А.В., Пинегин С.В., Ямпольский Г.Я., Михин Н.М., Комбалов В.С., Икромов У., Махкамов К.Х., Нуриев К.К., Мадазимов М.Т. ва бошқалар қатта ҳисса қўшганлар.

Маълум иш шароитлари учун материалларнинг ейилишга чидамлилиги тупроқнинг таркибидаги кварц доналарининг микдорига, уларнинг геометрик шаклига, зичлигига, намлигига ва бошқа хоссаларига боғлиқ бўлган ейилтириш қобилияти билан ифодаланади. Ишчи органлар материалининг ейилишга чидамлилигини иш шароитига боғлиқлигини ўрганиш устида Тененбаум М.М., Розенбаум А.Н., Рабинович А.Ш., Огрызков Е.Ц., Корушкин Б.Н., Костецкий Б.И. каби олимлар тадқиқотлар олиб боришган. Ушбу тадқиқотларнинг натижаларини таҳлил қилиш асосида ишчи органларнинг ейилиш жадаллигига тупроқнинг таркиби, намлиги, зичлиги, қаттиклиги, зарраларининг ўлчамлари ва шакли каби кўрсаткичлари кўпроқ таъсир кўрсатади деган хулоса чиқариш мумкин.

Маълумки, Ўзбекистонда, баҳорда кўпроқ ёғингарчилик кузатилади, ёзда ва кузнинг бошида ёғингарчилик кам бўлади, суғориш ишлари август ойининг ўрталаридан тўхтатилади ва шулар сабабли культиваторлар ва ҳайдов агрегатларининг иш шароити ёмонлашади.

Тупроқнинг физик-механик ва технологик хоссалари бўлган намлиги, зичлиги, қаттиклиги, ишқаланиш коэффициентлари тупроққа ишлов берадиган машиналарнинг эксплуатация кўрсаткичларига таъсир этади ва улар иш

органларининг геометрик шакли ва бошқа параметрларини танлашда ва асослашда муҳим омил бўлиб хизмат қилади.

Емирилиш жараёни нуқтаи-назардан тупроқнинг ейилтирувчи хоссаси - бу тупроқнинг, тупроқ таркибидаги ташкил этувчи зарралар ва қўшилмаларнинг кесувчи ва сирпанувчи таъсири натижасида, тупроққа ишлов берувчи машиналар иш органларининг ишчи юзаларини ейилтирувчи, уларнинг геометрик шакли ва ўлчамларини ўзгартирувчи хоссаси ҳисобланади.

Абразив ейилишнинг асосини абразив доналарнинг қирралари орқали деталлар юзасининг микроқирқилиш жараёни ташкил этади. Ейилиш жараёнининг жадаллигига абразив зарралар қирраларининг ўткирлиги ва сони катта таъсир кўрсатади. Тупроқ таркибида абразив зарралар сони қанча кўп бўлса ва уларнинг ўткир қирралари қанча кўп бўлса, улар деталларнинг юзаларига шунча кўп ейилтирувчи таъсир кўрсатади.

Абразив ейилиш қонуниятининг тўғрилиги тупроққа ишлов берувчи машиналар иш органларининг тупроққа ишқаланиб ейилишида ўз тасдиғини топади. Тупроққа ишлов берувчи иш органларининг ейилиш жадаллиги тупроқ таркибидаги қаттиқ абразив зарралар миқдорига ва уларни тупроқ массасида қанчалик маҳкам ўрнашганига боғлиқ бўлади.

Бундан ташқари, иш органларининг ейилиш жадаллиги тупроқнинг механик таркибига ва намлигига ҳамда унда тошли қўшимчаларнинг мавжудлигига боғлиқ бўлади. Тажрибаларда аниқланганки, абразив ейилишнинг жадаллиги ва катталиги тупроқнинг физик-механик хоссалари орқали аниқланади. Тупроқ таркибида 1,00...0,25 mm ли кум зарралари миқдори қанча кўп бўлса металлнинг абразив ейилиши шунча кўп бўлади. Бунда энг кўп таъсир кўрсатувчи омил бўлиб қаттиқ минераллар, яъни микроқаттиқлиги лемех пўлатининг микроқаттиқлиги (6,5 GPa гача) дан анча юқори 8,0...11,0 GPa бўлган кварц зарралари ҳисобланади. Ейилиш жадаллигида кварц зарраларининг шакли ҳам муҳим рол уйнайди. Зарралар қанча думалоқ бўлса, металл шунча кам ейилади, қанча нотекис бўлса, шунча жадал ейилади.

Бундан ташқари кум зарраларининг гилсимон ва гил тупроқларда қанчалик маҳкам ушлаб турилиши (айниқса, қуруқ тупроқда) ҳам муҳим аҳамият касб этади. Бунда кум зарралари иш органи юзасига шунча катта куч билан босилади, бу ўз навбатида ейилишни шунчалик жадаллаштиради.

Агар тупроқнинг намлиги оптимал бўлса, тупроқ шунча юмшоқ бўлади ва кум зарраларининг иш органларига босими шунча кам бўлади, ейилиш ҳам мос равишда минимал бўлади. Тупроқнинг зичлиги ва қаттиқлигини ортиши металлнинг абразив ейилишини орттиради.

Маълумки, ишлаш жараёнида лемехларнинг тумшук қисми, яъни долотаси энг тез ейилади. Бу лемехнинг тумшук қисми энг кўп юкланиш билан ишлашини билдиради. Лемехнинг долотаси тиф қисмига қараганда 2 марта тез ейилади. Бу

кўрсаткич турли тупроқ шароитлари учун тахминан бир хил.

Тупроқлар, ейилтирувчи хоссаси бўйича, бир-биридан кескин фарқ қилганлиги сабабли, турли тупроқларда иш органларининг ейилиш жадаллиги бир-биридан сезиларли даражада фарқ қилади. Агар иш органларининг турли қисмларига таъсир этадиган босимнинг бир-биридан фарқ қилишини ҳисобга олинса, улар ҳам бир хилда ейилмайди.

Плугларнинг иш органларида энг жадал ейиладиган қисмлари: лемехларда – тумшук қисми, ағдаргичда – олд юзаси, дала тахтасида – орқа қисми қалинлиги бўйича ва пастдан юқорига қараб ейилади. Лемехлар физик ейилишдан ташқари синиши ва эгилиши сабабли 10 % гача қисми яроқсизга чиқарилади. Шунинг учун ҳам, иш органларини яроқсизга чиқилишининг асосий сабабчиси ейилиш ҳисобланади.

Маълумки, ейилиш жадаллиги ейилиш режимига, тупроқнинг ейилтирувчи хоссасига ва ейиладиган юзанинг хоссаларига боғлиқ бўлади. Бунда, одатда, тупроқнинг ейилтирувчи хоссаси абразивга бериладиган босимнинг ўзгаришига тўғри пропорционал равишда ўзгариб боради, материалнинг нисбий ейилишга чидамлилиги ўзгармас катталик бўлиб қолади деб тасаввур қилинади.

Қуйидаги 1-жадвалда тупроқнинг фракцион таркиби бўйича унинг нисбий ейилтирувчи хоссалари келтирилган.

Андижон вилоятининг тупроқлари 1.1-жадвалда келтирилган 8 хилдан тўртта тупроқ типларига мансуб турлари мавжуд. Бунда умумий майдонга нисбатан суғориладиган типик ва оч тусли бўз тупроқлар (ўрта кумоқли) 25,5 % атрофида, ўтлоқи бўз тупроқлар (оғир ва ўрта кумоқли, айрим ҳолларда енгил кумоқли) 8,0 %, ўтлоқ тупроқлар (енгил кумоқли) 35%, ўтлоқи-ботқоқ (оғир кумоқдан кумлоққача) 10 % га яқин ва шўрхоқ ерлар (оғир кумоқдан кумлоққача) 9,6 %, бошқа тупроқлар 1,1% ни ташкил этади.

1.1-жадвал

Тупроқнинг фракцион таркиби бўйича нисбий ва абсолют ейилтирувчи хоссалари (эталон-кварц, босим – 0,1 МПа)

Тупроқнинг тури	Ўртача микдори, %		Нисбий ейилтирувчи хоссаси, m_{em}	Л53 пўлатининг $p = 0,1$ МПа босимдаги ейилиш жадаллиги, mm/ha
	қум	гил		
Қумлоқ	95	5	0,87	0,33
Қум тупроқ	85	15	0,62	0,24
Енгил кумоқ тупроқ	75	25	0,42	0,16
Ўртача кумоқ тупроқ	5	35	0,32	0,12
Оғир кумоқ тупроқ	50	50	0,22	0,08
Енгил соз тупроқ	5	65	0,15	0,06

Ўртача соз тупроқ	5	75	0,10	0,04
Оғир соз тупроқ	10	90	0,06	0,02
Кварц зарралари			1,0	0,38

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OB-HAVO SHAROITLARINING SHAHAR YO'NALISHLARIDA AVTOBUS QATNOVIGA TA'SIRI

Isroilov Sherzodbek

Andijon Mashinasozlik instituti tayanch doktoranti

Xomidov Anvarbek Ahmadjon o'g'li

Andijon Mashinasozlik instituti tayanch doktoranti

Annotatsiya: *Jamoat transporti jadvalini ishlab chiqishda ob-havo sharoitlarining marshrutdagi yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishiga ta'siri omili hisobga olinmaydi. Ushbu muammoni hal qilishning ilmiy yondashuvi avtobus yo'nalishi bo'yicha yo'lovchilar oqimi va ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlashni talab qiladi. Maqolada mualliflar ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari va avtobus yo'nalishidagi yo'lovchilar oqimi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganadilar.*

Kalit so'zlar: *yo'lovchi, jamoat transporti, ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari, harorat, sayohat vaqti, namlik, yog'ingarchilik.*

Jamoat transporti jadvali yo'lovchilarning o'ziga xos oqimiga bog'liq bo'lib, u odatda yo'lovchilar talabini, marshrut masofasini, marshrutdagi avtobus turlarini va ob-havo sharoitlarini hisobga olgan holda ishlab chiqiladi. Ob-havo sharoiti jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omillardan biridir. Jamoat transporti marshrut bo'ylab harakatlanayotganda, yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishi ko'rsatkichlari kunlik yog'ingarchilik darajasi, namlik, harorat va mavsumga bog'liq bo'ladi. Yo'lovchilar uchun chiptalarni sotish dinamikasini tavsiflovchi ko'rsatkichlardan biri bu ob-havo sharoitlarining ta'siri. Harorat va namlik jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sir qiluvchi eng muhim omillardir. Shu sababli, jamoat transporti jadvalini ishlab chiqishda ob-havo sharoitlarini hisobga olgan holda yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishi dinamikasini bashorat qilish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar o'tkazish muhimdir.

Sotilgan chiptalar soniga qarab yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sir qiluvchi bir qator ish kunlari va bayramlar, bayramlar, ta'tillar va yirik tadbirlardan tashqari, ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari harorat, namlik va yog'ingarchilik kabi ko'rsatkichlarga ham ta'sir qiladi. Ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimini bashorat qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Harorat - 40 dan past va yog'ingarchilik ish kunlari chiptalar savdosining oshishiga olib keladi, ya'ni jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimining taxminan 30% ga oshishiga olib keladi. Dam olish kunlari yog'ingarchilik va sovuq harorat sharoitida jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimi ish kunlariga nisbatan sezilarli darajada kamayadi. Ob-havo sharoitiga qarab yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishi yo'lovchilarning boradigan joylari va joylashuvining geografik ehtimoli bilan bog'liq. Ushbu masalaga ilmiy yondashuv ob-havo va jamoat

transportida yo'lovchilar oqimi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlashni talab qiladi. Maqolada biz shahar avtobus yo'nalishlarida yo'lovchilar oqimi va ob-havo sharoiti o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganamiz.

Bugungi kunda Andijonda doimiy aholi, mehmonlar, xodimlar va talabalar soni kundan-kunga o'sib bormoqda. Ko'pgina yo'lovchilar uchun transport xizmatlari "Alpomish me'rosi" MCHJning avtobus yo'nalishlari hisoblanadi. Yo'lovchilarga transport xizmati ko'rsatish sifatini oshirish maqsadida avtobus yo'nalishlarida yo'lovchi oqimi o'zgarishi va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar o'tkazish dolzarbdir.

Dunyo bo'ylab tadqiqotchilar ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun ko'plab ilmiy tadqiqotlar o'tkazdilar. Masalan, meteorologiya bo'limi, Freie Universitat Berlin, Germaniya, K. M. Nissen, N. Becker, o. Dahne, M. Rahe, J. Scheffler, M. Solle va u Ulbrich tadqiqotchilari Berlindagi ob-havo sharoiti yo'lovchilar oqimiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganishdi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, Berlin jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimi chiptalarni sotish bilan belgilanadi. Tahlilda 7 yoshdan oshgan yo'lovchilar va elektron to'lov asosida jamoat transportidan foydalanadigan yo'lovchilar hisobga olindi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, Berlin yomon ob-havo sharoitida haydovchilar tomonidan sotilgan avtobus chiptalarning ulushini oshirdi [1].

Technological University Dublin – Blanchardstown Campusa Markus Hofmann tadqiqotchilari va Margaret O'Mahon turli ob-havo sharoitida avtobuslarning ishlashini o'rganishdi. Tadqiqot davomida dispetcherlarga avtobuslar jadvalini tuzishda ob-havo sharoitlarini hisobga olish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi. Tadqiqot yiliga 12 oy davomida ob-havo sharoitida yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tahlil qildi [2].

Kelajak shaharlari instituti, Gonkong Xitoy universiteti, Shatin, yangi Territories, Gonkong tadqiqotchisi Sui Tada, va Jonatan Korkoranb, Fransisko Rowec, Mark Nikman avtobusda sayohat qilish vaqtiga qarab mahalliy ob-havo sharoitlariga bog'liq modellarni ishlab chiqish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar olib borishdi. Tadqiqot mintaqaning funksional imkoniyatlarini hisobga olgan holda ob-havoning avtobuslarning soatlik harakatiga ta'sirini modellashtirdi. Tadqiqot tranzit Smart-kartalardagi ma'lumotlar to'plamidagi avtobuslarning kechikkan ta'sirini va vaqt birliklarida batafsil ob-havo o'lchovlarini olish uchun hisoblab chiqilgan [3].

Avstraliyaning Kvinslend texnologiya universiteti tadqiqotchilari Syeed Anta Kashfi va professor Jonatan Bunker dotsenti ob-havoning avtobuslar harakatiga ta'siri bo'yicha tadqiqot o'tkazdilar. Tadqiqot noqulay ob-havo sharoitlarining avtobus qatnoviga ta'sirini o'rganib chiqdi. Avtobus yo'nalishlarining ob-havoga bog'liqligi va sayohat vaqti, shuningdek, noqulay ob-havo sharoitida avtobuslar harakatiga xususiy transportning ta'siri masalalari o'rganildi [4].

Andijon shahar jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar tashishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni o'rganish maqsadida rivojlangan mamlakatlarning jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar tashishni bashorat qilish tajribasi, transportga ta'sir etuvchi barcha omillar va jamoat transportida yo'lovchilarga xizmat ko'rsatishning zamonaviy usullari tahlil qilindi.

Andijonda hozirda 3,0 milliondan ortiq aholi istiqomat qiladi. 2020 yilda Viloyatimizga 8 500 sayyoh tashrif buyurdi. Agar yil davomida Andijonda jamoat transportida tashilgan yo'lovchilar soni tahlil qilinsa, bu 104 725 000 kishini tashkil etadi. Andijonda yo'lovchilar jamoat transporti tanloviga ega, chunki yo'lovchilarga faqatgina turli transport turlari xizmat qiladi. Bularga damaslar, avtobuslar, mikroavtobuslar va taksilar kiradi.

Yo'lovchilar oqimini o'rganish ish kunlari va dam olish kunlari amalga oshiriladi. Dunyo olimlarining asarlari tahliliga ko'ra, dam olish kunlaridagi ob-havo sharoiti jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar aylanmasiga ko'proq ta'sir qiladi. Andijonda jamoat transporti yo'lovchilari oqimiga ta'sir qiluvchi yana bir omil-maktab o'quvchilari va talabalar ta'til va maktab, texnik va universitet ta'tillarida jamoat transportidan foydalanmasliklari. Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, ushbu ta'sir omili jamoat transportining tirbandligida, ya'ni ertalab soat 7 dan 9 gacha bo'lgan vaqt oralig'ida namoyon bo'ladi. Yo'lovchilar oqimini aniqlashning bir necha yo'li mavjud. Buni sotilgan chiptalarga nisbatan yo'lovchilar oqimini hisoblash va oylik to'lovli elektron kartalar asosida sayohat qilayotgan yo'lovchilar foizini qo'shish orqali aniqlash mumkin. Yo'lovchilar oqimining umumiy hisob-kitobi xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi asosida chiptalarni sotishga asoslangan. Yo'lovchilar oqimi yomg'irli, sovuq, quruq, namligi past kunlarda va hatto bulutsiz kunlarda o'zgaradi. Dam olish kunlari tunda noqulay ob-havo sharoitida ham yo'lovchilar oqimi sezilarli darajada kamayadi. Ob-havoning jamoat transportiga ta'sirini ikki yo'l bilan o'rganish tavsiya etiladi: mutlaq va nisbiy. [5]

Mutlaq usul avtobus haydovchilaridan qat'i nazar, yo'lovchilar oqimini o'zgartirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Nisbiy ma'noda, avtobus haydovchilariga ob-havoning ta'siri bilan bog'liq harakat tushuniladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, kutish vaqtlari va jamoat transporti joylarining qulayligi noqulay ob-havo sharoitida yo'lovchilar oqimiga ham ta'sir qiladi. Bu jamoat transportida yo'lovchilar oqimiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

1-Rasm. Andijon Shahar harorati va yog'ingarchilikning umumiy ko'rsatkichlari
Temperature - harorat
Rainfall – yog'ingarchilik ko'rsatkichi

Ma'lumotlarga ko'ra hikersbay.com, Andijonda ko'p yillar davomida eng yuqori harorat iyulga, eng past harorat esa yanvarga to'g'ri keladi. Yog'ingarchilik

ma'lumotlarini tahlil qilar ekanmiz, shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, eng ko'p yog'ingarchilik mart oyida, eng kam yog'ingarchilik esa iyulda sodir bo'lgan. Meteorologik ko'rsatkichlarning tashkilotchilari ham bor edi. Shuningdek, atmosfera bosimi, quyosh chiqishi va botish vaqti va shamolning o'rtacha tezligi kabi ko'rsatkichlar mavjud [6].

Quyida shahar jamoat transporti rejimiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omillar ko'rib chiqiladi.

- kunduzgi vaqt (eng yuqori ish vaqti - odatda 700 dan 900 gacha va 17:00 dan 19:00 gacha, bo'sh vaqt);
- * mavsum (mavsum, oy);
- * ish kunlari (ish kunlari va dam olish kunlari);
- * ob-havo sharoiti (harorat, yog'ingarchilik va namlik);
- * dam olish kunlari (maktab va kollej ta'tillari, dam olish kunlari bayramdan tashqari);
- * bayram kunlari (1 yanvar - yangi yil, 8 mart - xalqaro xotin - qizlar kuni, 21 mart - Navro'z, 9 may - g'alaba kuni, 1 sentyabr - Mustaqillik kuni, 1 oktyabr - o'qituvchi va ustoz kuni, 8 dekabr - Konstitutsiya kuni, Ramazon va boshqalar.);
- * yirik tadbirlar (sport musobaqalari, konsertlar, konferentsiyalar, simpoziumlar);
- * geopozitsiya-shahar va viloyatning demografik va boshqa ko'rsatkichlari:

O'zbekiston Respublikasida transport turlari bo' yicha yo'lovchilar oqimi ko'rsatkichlari

Jadval №1	Yillar	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Yo'lovchilar tashildi, million yo'lovchi		4 909,9	5 169,9						
		5 380,0	5 560,4						
		5 679,0	5 951,5	6 025,1	5 240,4				
Temir yo'l transporti				17,4	19,1	20,1	20,5	21,1	22,1
Avtomobil transporti		4815,8 1)	5079,0 1)	5293,2 1)	5480,8 1)	5			
	591,3	5 852,8	5 915,2	5 192,9					

1) aniqlangan ma'lumotlar

2) dastlabki ma'lumotlar

1-jadvalda keltirilgan yo'lovchi oqimi dinamikasiga ko'ra, 2016-2023 yillarda mamlakat transport tizimining umumiy yo'lovchi aylanmasida avtomobil transporti ulushi 95-99% darajasida barqaror bo'lib qoldi. 2016-2023 yillarda avtomobil transportida yo'lovchi oqimi o'sishi har yili o'rtacha 4-6 foizni tashkil etdi.

Biz 2023 yilda Andijondagi "Alpomish merosi" MCHJ avtobus parkiga tegishli avtobuslarda tashilgan yo'lovchilar soniga nisbatan ob-havo ko'rsatkichlarining yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sirini tahlil qildik. (2-jadval)

Jadval № 2

2023 yil uchun ob-havoning o'rtacha ko'rsatkichlari va avtobus parki avtobuslarida yo'lovchilar soni

Oylar Yo'lovchilar soni (Q) O'rtacha ob-havo harorati (t) Namlik darajasi (%) Tuproqning o'rtacha harorati (t) Yog'ingarchilik (mm)

Qor qoplami (balandligi sm)

Yanvar	817 173	5,6	61	3	74,5	3
Fevral	804 373	5,7	61	5	30,6	6
Mart	885 662	12,9	56	13	47,1	0
April	922 657	15,8	11,7	17	46,2	0
May	903 886	22,5	42	29	0,8	0
Iyun	782 579	25,5	39	32	55,6	0
Iyul	761 087	21,4	30	39	0	0
Avgust	784 715	27,5	33	34	0	0

Rasm:2 yo'lovchi oqimi va o'rtacha ob-havo ko'rsatkichlari

Ob – havo sharoitlarining yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sirini o'rganish natijasida biz 2-rasmni tuzdik, unda Alpomish me'rosi avtobuslari tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan avtobus yo'nalishlarida ob-havo o'zgarishining yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'siri darajasi ko'rsatilgan.

Tahlil qilingan yilning eng yuqori harorati iyul avgust oyida bo'lgan. Ushbu jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, yo'lovchilar oqimining eng past darajasi haroratning eng yuqori oylariga to'g'ri keladi. Yo'lovchilar oqimiga ta'sir qiluvchi yana bir omil shundaki, maktab o'quvchilari va talabalar iyul-avgust oylarida ta'tilda. Yo'lovchilar oqimining ko'payishi oylari aprel va dekabr oylaridir. Dekabr oyida biz havo harorati o'rtacha -2 ga tushib ketganini ko'rdik, bu esa o'z navbatida o'sha paytda yo'lovchilar oqimining ko'payishiga olib keldi. Yo'lovchilar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalariga ko'ra, past harorat va minuslarda ular shaxsiy transportga qaraganda jamoat transportidan ko'proq foydalanadilar.

3-Rasm. Yo'lovchi oqimi va o'rtacha namlik ko'rsatkichlari (%)

Tahlil paytida yo'lovchilarning o'rtacha oylik oqimi va ob-havo namligi o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganayotganda (rasm. 3) eng ko'p yo'lovchi oqimi aprel oyida, namlik darajasi eng past bo'lgan paytda kuzatilgan.

4-Rasm. Yog'ingarchilikning (mm) yo'lovchi oqimiga ta'sirining o'rtacha statistik ko'rsatkichlari

Iyul oyida qayd etilgan yo'lovchilarning eng kam soni avgust, minimal yog'ingarchilik kuzatilganda (rasm. 4), shuningdek, maktab va talabalar ta'tillari davrlari bilan bog'liq edi.

Jamoat transporti harakati paytida ob-havo sharoiti unga to'liq ta'sir qiladi. Shuning uchun jamoat transporti xizmatlarining sifati ob-havo sharoitlariga ham bog'liq. Ob-havo ko'rsatkichlarining avtobuslarning tayyorligiga ta'siri asosan past harorat davrida namoyon bo'ladi. Yo'nalishdagi noqulay ob-havo sharoiti silliq yo'lda harakatlanish tezligining ma'lum darajada pasayishi, yomg'ir va tumanda ko'rinishning yomonlashishi, yomg'ir va past haroratlarda yo'lovchilar oqimining o'zgarishi, avtobuslarning manevrliligi va tirbandlikning oshishi bilan bog'liq muammolarga olib keladi. Ushbu salbiy ta'sirlar jamoat transportining umumiy sayohat vaqtining ko'payishiga va xizmat ko'rsatish sifatining pasayishiga olib keladi. Marshrutda jamoat transporti vaqtining 35-40% oraliq stantsiyalarda to'xtash (to'xtash) ga to'g'ri keladi. Marshrut vaqti va aloqa tezligi yuqoridagi ko'rsatkichlar ta'sirida o'zgaradi.

Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlaymizki, ob-havo ko'rsatkichlarini hisobga olmagan holda jamoat transporti harakatini tashkil etish avtobusning marshrut bo'ylab harakatlanish vaqtiga va xizmat ko'rsatish sifatiga salbiy ta'sir qiladi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, jamoat transporti rejimida ob-havo ko'rsatkichlarini hisobga olmaslik xizmat ko'rsatish sifatining pasayishiga olib keladi.

Avtobus qatnovi jadvalining rejadan chetga chiqishiga ta'sir qiluvchi bunday omillarni jadvalni ishlab chiqishda hisobga olish tavsiya etiladi. Jadvalni ishlab chiqishda ob-havo ko'rsatkichlarining har birini hisobga olish, avtobuslar assortimentini ta'minlash va yo'lovchilarga xizmat ko'rsatishning ishonchligini oshirish mumkin.

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МЕТОДИКА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СУЩЕСТВУЮЩЕЙ
ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПАССАЖИРСКИХ ГОРОДСКИХ ПЕРЕВОЗОК.

Исроилов Ш.Ш.

Андижанский машиностроительный институт.

Хомидов А.А.

Андижанский машиностроительный институт.

Аннотация: Работа включает в себя методику разработки мероприятий по проектированию вновь открываемых маршрутов или совершенствования существующей организации перевозок с целью повышения качества обслуживания пассажиров и повышения использования подвижного состава или снижения затрат, экономии трудовых и материальных ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: городские пассажирские перевозки, технология пассажирских перевозок, расписание движения, технология пассажиро перевозок.

Abstract: The work includes a methodology for developing measures for the design of newly opened routes or improving the existing organization of transportation in order to improve the quality of passenger service and increase the use of rolling stock or reduce costs, saving labor and material resources.

Key words: urban passenger transportation, passenger transportation technology, timetable, passenger transportation technology.

Вступление. Городской пассажирский транспорт родского хозяйства, функционирование которой – подсистема повлияет на качество жизни населения, эффективность городского хозяйства и возможность использования градостроительного и социально-экономического потенциала города. Под технологией перевозки пассажиров понимается совокупность методов перевозки пассажиров, научная дисциплина, учающая различные закономерности, наблюдаемые в процессе перевозки пассажиров и багажа. Суть маршрутной технологии пассажирских перевозок заключается в организации движения подвижного состава по одному и тому же маршруту в виде последовательности повторяющихся циклов транспортировки – рейсов. Основными принципами маршрутной технологии являются: определенность маршрута и стабильность его трассы; регулярность движения транспортных средств по маршруту и расписание движения по расписанию; совпадение интересов пассажи-ров, пользующихся маршрутом,

выраженных в соответствии с пассажирской корреспонденцией и маршрутом; контроль за работой транспортных средств на маршруте и осуществление диспетчерского контроля.

Методика совершенствования существующей организации пассажирских городских перевозок включает несколько этапов:

1. Характеристика маршрутной сети, изучение схемы маршрутной сети со всеми остановочными пунктами и характеристикой точек тяготения, а также опасных участков.

2. Анализ работы подвижного состава на линии, которая включает:

– изучение подвижного состава (ПС) работающего на маршрутах и его соответствие пассажиропотоку на маршруте и комфортабельность поездки пассажиров;

– соотношение автобусов работающих на маршруте по часам суток в выходные и будние дни, подсчет автомобилей – часов работы на маршруте в соответствии с существующим расписанием;

– подсчет интервалов движения автобусов на маршрутной сети по средствам натуральных наблюдений;

– затраты на эксплуатацию ПС, работающего на существующей маршрутной сети.

3. Диспетчерское управление движения автобусов на маршруте. На данном этапе необходимо изучить: как осуществляется диспетчерское управление и как контролируется регулярность движения ПС (фактическая и запланированная); как происходит сбор и обработка информации об осуществляемых перевозках; функционал работников диспетчерской службы; работу внутри парковой и линейной диспетчеризации, оценить применяемые технические средства диспетчерского управления и обработки информации.

4. Анализ организации системы оплаты проезда и провоза багажа. На данном этапе необходимо проанализировать систему оплаты проезда по маршрутам (кондукторное обслуживание, автоматизированные системы или сбор платы водителем), внимание следует уделить тарифам на маршруте (единый тариф или по тарифным участкам), изучить процентное соотношение пассажиров имеющих право на льготный и бесплатный проезд и систему возмещения затрат по их проезду, исследовать как организован контроль полноты сбора выручки на маршруте, его частота и эффективность

5. Анализ технико-эксплуатационных показателей работы ПС и организация труда водителей. Расчет и сравнение с нормативами показателей качества перевозок являются важной составной частью изучения существующей организации перевозок пассажиров. Под технико-эксплуатационными показателями (ТЭП) понимают систему взаимосвязанных первичных и расчетных показателей, характеризующих возможное и фактическое использование технического объекта в существующих эксплуатационных условиях.

К ТЭП маршрутных автобусов относятся: общая пассажироместность автобусов; пробег автобусов по маршрутам; коэффициент использования пробега;

общее число рейсов по маршрутам; эксплуатационная скорость движения; предоставленная пассажироместность; статический коэффициент наполняемости; динамический коэффициент наполняемости; коэффициент регулярности движения; число пассажироместо-дней в хозяйстве; число пассажироместо-дней в работе; число пассажироместо-часов в работе.

После проведения анализа существующей организации перевозок необходимо указать выявленные недостатки и существующие неиспользованные резервы способные улучшить качество обслуживания пассажирских перевозок. Заключение анализа влияют на мероприятия по оптимизации пассажироперевозок по маршруту.

Технология пассажироперевозок должна учитывать следующие аспекты:

- соответствие пассажиропотока и метода организации движения автобусов на маршруте;
- возможность применения скоростного, экспрессного, полуэкспрессного или укороченного варианта движения;
- выбор и расчет оптимального ПС в зависимости от пассажиропотока и точек тяготения;
- выбор и расчет технико-эксплуатационных показателей использования ПС на маршруте.

Основной задачей совершенствования функционирующей или проектируемой организации пассажироперевозок на маршрутной сети должно являться существенное улучшение транспортного обслуживания пассажиров, повышения качества перевозок и повышение эффективности использования ПС. При совершенствовании организации пассажирских перевозок необходимо обеспечить нормативный уровень показателей качества перевозок. Основными показателями качества пассажирских перевозок являются: время, затрачиваемое на перемещение; безопасность пассажирских перевозок; комфорт поездки (регулярность движения и наполнение ПС).

При организации движения автобусов на проектируемых или существующих маршрутах одной из основных задач является выбор типа и расчет требуемого числа ТС. Правильно выбранный по вместимости тип автобусов и верно выполненный расчет потребного числа автобусов на маршруте оказывают решающее влияние на качество обслуживания пассажиров и эффективность работы ПС.

Если на маршруте вводятся в действие или прекращают работу объекты социального, промышленного или культурно-бытового назначения, то это может повлиять на изменение пассажиропотока.

Совершенствование городских пассажирских перевозок на маршруте может включать изменение графика движения автобусов, введение скоростных, экспрессных или укороченных графиков для части автобусов рассматриваемого

маршрута. Грамотно разработанное расписание движения автобусов на маршруте обеспечивает высокий уровень организации пассажирских перевозок, эффективного использования ПС и снижения себестоимости перевозок.

Расписание движения автобусов—это важный документ, который регламентирующий режим движения ПС на маршруте, время начала и окончания работы на маршруте, интервалы движения по часам суток, а также описывает форму организации труда водителей. В связи с этим при составлении расписания движения на маршруте следует учитывать результаты обследования пассажиропотока для того, чтобы обеспечить:

- минимальные затраты пассажира на ожидании и перемещение по маршруту;
- регулярность и соблюдение расписания движения на маршруте;
- максимальную скорость движения автобусов по маршруту с соблюдением установленных ПДД;
- более эффективное использование ПС на маршруте согласно технико-эксплуатационным показателем.

Эффективность и качество пассажирских перевозок во многом зависит от типа подвижного состава, работающего на маршрутной сети, степени его соответствия пассажиропотокам и условиям эксплуатации. Выбор типа ПС по вместимости – задача многокритериальная и противоречива по отношению перевозчика и потребителя пассажирской услуги. Выбор типа автобуса по вместимости зависит от многих факторов: объема и расстояния перевозок, условий и методов организации движения, вида перевозок и режимов движения, дорожных и климатических условий и т.д.

Основой организации обслуживания на маршруте являются результаты анализа существующей организации перевозок пассажиров по маршрутам.

Совершенствование пассажироперевозок должно быть направлено, в первую очередь, на устранение недостатков существующей организации, выявленных при ее изучении, на внедрение в транспортный процесс неиспользованных резервов и новых форм организации труда и методов организации перевозок.

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STRUCTURE AND LIFESTYLE OF UNGULATE FISH

Umaraliyeva Go'zal Komiljonovna

The sheep head fish is a deep-bodied, compressed marine fish with rounded sharp vertebrae. Fish usually reach 10-20 inches, but in some cases can grow up to 35 inches! It has a hard mouth and stubborn teeth, which are very similar to human teeth.

The sheep's head is of the euralaline type, that is, they are collected from waters with a salinity of 0-35 PPT (equal to a thousand parts). They are close enough to shore and feed on shell creatures when they do not spawn.

They thrive well in brackish waters, especially at the confluence of rainwater runoff with brackish rivers. Due to the obvious advantage of feeding, sheep are prone to environmental extreme fluctuations. Their tolerance to pollution and reduced oxygen levels is particularly low and they tend to leave contaminated water bodies. For example, there is a bay named Sheepshead Bay in Brooklyn, New York, named after this fish, but its fish have abandoned this cove due to increased pollution levels.

Sharp and thick teeth begin to appear when the length of the sheep's head fish is only 4.5 mm, and after the fish reaches a length of about 15 mm, all teeth appear. At the same time, its back teeth become adult teeth.

There are two rows of teeth on the lower jaw and three rows on the upper jaw. This heavy-toothed tooth allows sheepfish to easily crush and crush shellfish that these fish prefer to feed on.

Sheep head fish are omnivorous and therefore have a very varied diet. They can absorb almost any organic matter that can be found at the bottom of the seabed or even on vertical hard surfaces, including vegetation. These diverse feeders are known to consume small vertebrates, invertebrates, and plant material. Some studies have shown that they feed on more than 100 different species!

A team of researchers in Mississippi found that mutton fish 5-15 inches long were capable of eating molluscs. When they grew up, they switched to other delicious dishes, including shrimp, worms, fish and other crustaceans. Curiously, when seagrass and algae were too abundant, mutton fish fed them too much.

Muttonfish are characterized by their diet, location, weather, and availability of food.

Many studies suggest that sheep play an important role in maintaining marine ecological balance. They help, in particular, regulate fauna on hard surfaces under water, such as Immobile barnacles or species that crawl or float on the ground. Due to its propensity to consume many species, sheephead fish provide basic service while maintaining the biodiversity of the watershed.

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ANATOMY OF FISH

Umaraliyeva Go'zal Komiljonovna

Fish habitats are various bodies of water of the planet: lakes, lakes, rivers, seas and oceans.

Fish occupy very large territories, in any case the ocean area exceeds 70% of the Earth's surface. To this, it becomes clear that the deepest depressions penetrate to a depth of 11 thousand meters to the bottom of the ocean, and what cavities the fish have. Aquatic life is characterized by a great variety, which could not but affect the appearance of Fish, and their body shape led to such a variety as underwater life itself.

The fish has gill wings on its head, lips and mouth, nostrils and eyes. The head merges very smoothly into the body. There is a body that ends in a tail from the branched wings to the anal fin.

Fin serve as movement organs for fish. In fact, they are skin tumors that rely on bone fin rays. For fish, the caudal fin is the most important. On the sides of the body, on its underside, there are pairs of pelvic and pectoral fins that correspond to the Hind and forelimbs of vertebrates living on Earth. Paired wings can be arranged differently in different fish species. The Dorsal fin is located on the upper body of the fish, and below the anal fin is next to the tail. In addition, it should be noted that the number of anal and dorsal fins in fish can vary.

Most fish have an organ on the sides of the body that senses the flow of water, which is called the "lateral line". Thanks to this, even a blind fish can catch moving prey without encountering obstacles. The visible part of the lateral line consists of perforated scales.

Through these holes, water enters the canal that runs through the body, where the ends of nerve cells that run through the canal are felt. The lateral line in the fish can be rigid, continuous, or completely absent. Some species of fish, such as cats or carp, can see antennae around the mouth. These organs perform a tactile function and are also used to determine the taste of food. Many deep-sea fish, such as photoblepharon, anchovies, fish, and deep fisherman, have shiny organs. On fish scales, you can sometimes find protective spines located on different parts of the body. For example, the body of hedgehog fish is almost completely covered with thorns. Some species of fish, such as warts, Sea Dragon and scorpion fish, have special attack and defense organs - poisonous glands, which are located at the base of the fin rays and spines.

The sensory organs of fish are very well developed. The eyes are able to accurately recognize objects at close range and distinguish colors. The fish senses sounds through the inner ear located inside the skull and smells through the nostrils.

In the oral cavity, the skin of the lips and antennae - taste organs, which allow the fish to distinguish between salty, sour and sweet. The lateral line, due to the sensitive cells located inside it, is sensitive to changes in water pressure and transmits signals related to the brain.

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**UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDAGI PEDADGOGLARDA O'Z USTIDA
ISHLASH SAMARADORLIGINI EMPIRIK ASOSLARI**

Razakov Farxod Kuvandikovich

Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti o'qituvchisi

razakovfarxod1@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: *ushbu maqolada umumta'lim maktablaridagi pedagoglarda o'z ustida ishlash samaradorligi bo'yicha olib borilgan tajriba-sinov ishlarining yakuniy natijalari tadbiq etilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *umumta'lim maktablari, kadrlar, o'qituvchi, rivojlanish, harakatlar strategiyasi, o'quvchilar*

Umumta'lim maktablariga pedagoglari o'z ustida ishlash faoliyatini tarbiyalashning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari va ularni tadqiq qilish usullarining psixologik jihatlari tahlil etish masalasini o'rganish pedagoglardagi ta'lim jarayonidagi bilimlardan foydalanish va o'zlashtirilgan bilim-malakalar asosida kasbiy faoliyatni qiyinchiliklarsiz pedagogik faoliyatni amalga oshirish muhim masalalardan sanaladi.

Dastlab, Samarqand viloyatida faoliyat olib borayotgan pedagoglarning shaxs intilish darajasi va o'z-o'zini baholash sifatlarini aniqlash so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlik qiymatlari navbatdagi jadvalda aks ettirilgan.

3.1-jadval

Shaxs intilish darajasi va o'z-o'zini baholash so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi korrelyatsiya ko'rsatkichlari (K.Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti bo'yicha)

Ichki motiv	Musobaqalashuv motivi	0,367*
	Topshiriqlarning murakkabligi	0,545**
	Irodaviy quvvat	0,409*
	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,395*
	Intellekt	0,372*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,417*
Qochish motivi	Musobaqalashuv motivi	0,348*
	Irodaviy quvvat	0,304*
	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,421*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	-0,329*
Musobaqalashuv motivi	Topshiriqlarning murakkabligi	0,520**

	Sog'lik	0,364*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	- 0,322*
Topshiriqlarning murakkabligi	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,555**
	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,369*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,314*
Irodaviy quvvat	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,540**
	Intellekt	- 0,317*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,434*
O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	Intellekt	- 0,380*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,375*
Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	Sog'lik	- 0,316*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,344*
Sog'lik	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,446

Izoh: * $r \leq 0,05$, ** $r \leq 0,01$.

Umumorta ta'lim maktabi pedagoglarida o'z ustida ishlash faoliyatini tarbiyalashning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari bo'yicha tadqiqotdan olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, pedagoglarining shaxs intilish darajasi va o'z-o'zini baholash faktorlari ortasidagi imkoniyatlarni o'rganish so'rovnomlari bo'yicha shkalalar orasidagi korrelyatsion aloqalar ko'proq ichki motiv faktorlari bilan ya'ni musobaqalashuv motivi ($r=0,367$, $r \leq 0,05$), topshiriqlarning murakkabligi ($r=0,545$, $r \leq 0,01$), irodaviy quvvat ($r=0,409$, $r \leq 0,05$), natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,395$, $r \leq 0,05$), intellekt ($r=0,372$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,417$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, qochish motivi shkalasi musobaqalashuv motivi ($r=0,348$, $r \leq 0,05$), irodaviy quvvat ($r=0,304$, $r \leq 0,05$), o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,421$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,329$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, musobaqalashuv motivi shkalasi topshiriqlarning murakkabligi ($r=0,520$, $r \leq 0,01$) sog'liq ($r=0,364$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,322$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, topshiriqlarning murakkabligi shkalasi natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,555$, $r \leq 0,01$), o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,369$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,314$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, irodaviy quvvat shkalasi o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,540$, $r \leq 0,01$), intellekt ($r=0,317$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,434$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi shkalasi intellekt ($r=0,380$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,375$, $r \leq 0,05$)

faktorlari bilan, natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi sog'lik ($r=0,316$, $r\leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,344$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, sog'lik shkalasi o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,446$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlar orasida o'rta darajada korrelyatsion aloqalar kuzatilayotganligini ko'rish mumkin. Keyingi jadvalda Buxoro viloyati pedagoglarining o'z-o'ziga munosabat va o'z xulq-atvorini tartibga solish so'rovnomalari bo'yicha o'zaro korrelyatlari keltirilgan.

3.2-jadval

Shaxsning o'z-o'ziga munosabati va o'z xulq-atvorini tartibga solish so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi korrelyatsiya ko'rsatkichlari (K.Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti bo'yicha)

O'z-o'zini idora qilish	O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash	0,312*
	O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	0,375*
	Rejalashtirish	0,510**
	Natijalarni baholash	0,391*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,375*
O'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi	O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	-0,317*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,349*
	Mustaqillik	0,307*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,378*
O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash	Rejalashtirish	0,345*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,478*
O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	Rejalashtirish	-0,397*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,565**
	Mustaqillik	0,345*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,530**
Rejalashtirish	Natijalarni baholash	0,338*
	Mustaqillik	0,347*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	-0,459*
Natijalarni baholash	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning	0,439*

	umumiy darajasi	
Mustaqillik	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,371*

Izoh: * $r \leq 0,05$, ** $r \leq 0,01$.

Samarqand viloyatining shaxsning o'z-o'ziga munosabati va o'z xulq-atvorini tartibga solish so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqador faktorlar orasidagi korrelyatsion aloqalar ko'proq o'z-o'zini idora qilish shkalasi o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash ($r=0,312$, $r \leq 0,05$), o'z-o'zini qabul qilish ($r=0,375$, $r \leq 0,05$), rejalashtirish ($r=0,510$, $r \leq 0,01$), natijalarni baholash ($r=0,391$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,375$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi shkalasi o'z-o'zini qabul qilish ($r=0,317$, $r \leq 0,05$), natijalarni baholash ($r=0,349$, $r \leq 0,05$), mustaqillik ($r=0,367$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,530$, $r \leq 0,01$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash shkalasi rejalashtirish ($r=0,345$, $r \leq 0,05$) va natijalarni baholash ($r=0,478$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'zini qabul qilish shkalasi rejalashtirish ($r=0,397$, $r \leq 0,05$), natijalarni baholash ($r=0,565$, $r \leq 0,01$), mustaqillik ($r=0,345$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,530$, $r \leq 0,01$) faktorlari bilan, rejalashtirish shkalasi natijalarni baholash ($r=0,338$, $r \leq 0,05$), mustaqillik ($r=0,347$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,459$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, natijalarni baholash shkalasi o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,439$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, mustaqillik shkalasi o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,371$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlar orasida o'rta darajada korrelyatsion aloqalarga kirishganligini ko'rish mumkin.

Keyingi jadvalda Buxoro viloyatida faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan pedagoglarining shaxs intilishi va o'z-o'zini baholash darajasi so'rovnomalari bo'yicha o'zaro korrelyatlari aks ettirilgan.

3.3-jadval

Shaxs intilish darajasi va o'z-o'zini baholash so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi korrelyatsiya ko'rsatkichlari (K.Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti bo'yicha)

Ichki motiv	Qochish motivi	-0,486*
	Irodaviy quvvat	0,364*
	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,367*
	Intellekt	0,401*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,399*

Qochish motivi	Musobaqalashuv motivi	0,321*
	Sog'lik	0,505**
	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,370*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	-0,354*
Musobaqalashuv motivi	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,435*
	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,695**
Topshiriqlarning murakkabligi	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	-0,374*
	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,394*
	O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	0,312*
	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,370*
Irodaviy quvvat	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,347*
	Intellekt	-0,335*
O'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,361*
	Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	0,474*
Natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi	Intellekt	0,397*
	Sog'lik	-0,387*
Sog'lik	O'z-o'ziga ishonch	0,332*
	Intellekt	0,367*

Izoh: * $r \leq 0,05$, ** $r \leq 0,01$.

O'z ustida ishlash faoliyatini tarbiyalashning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari bo'yicha shaxs intilish darajasi va o'z-o'zini baholash o'rtasidagi imkoniyatlarni o'rganish so'rovnomalari bo'yicha faktorlar orasidagi korrelyatsion aloqalar ko'proq ichki motiv faktorlari bilan ya'ni qochish motivi ($r=0,486$, $r \leq 0,05$), irodaviy quvvat ($r=0,364$, $r \leq 0,05$), o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,367$, $r \leq 0,05$), intellekt ($r=0,401$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,399$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, qochish motivi shkalasi musobaqalashuv motivi ($r=0,321$, $r \leq 0,05$), sog'lik ($r=0,505$, $r \leq 0,01$), o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,370$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,354$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, musobaqalashuv motivi shkalasi o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,435$, $r \leq 0,05$) natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,695$, $r \leq 0,01$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,374$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, topshiriqlarning murakkabligi shkalasi

natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,394$, $r\leq 0,05$), o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi ($r=0,312$, $r\leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,370$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, irodaviy quvvat shkalasi natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,347$, $r\leq 0,05$), intellekt ($r=0,335$, $r\leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,361$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z imkoniyatlarining bahosi shkalasi natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi ($r=0,474$, $r\leq 0,05$) va intellekt ($r=0,397$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, natijalarning kutilganlik darajasi sog'lik ($r=0,387$, $r\leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'ziga ishonch ($r=0,332$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, sog'lik shkalasi intellekt ($r=0,367$, $r\leq 0,05$) faktorlari orasida yuqori darajada korrelyatsion aloqalar namoyon bo'lganligini ko'rish mumkin.

3.4-jadval

Shaxsning o'z-o'ziga munosabati va o'z xulq-atvorini tartibga solish so'rovnomalari o'rtasidagi korrelyatsiya ko'rsatkichlari (K.Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti bo'yicha)

O'z-o'zini idora qilish	O'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi	0,336*
	O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	0,315*
	Mustaqillik	0,435*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,396*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	-0,581**
O'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi	O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	-0,368*
	O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash	0,391*
	Mustaqillik	0,344*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,374*
O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash	Rejalashtirish	0,403*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,342*
	Mustaqillik	0,446*
O'z-o'zini qabul qilish	Rejalashtirish	-0,413*
	Natijalarni baholash	0,511**
	Mustaqillik	0,326*
Rejalashtirish	Natijalarni baholash	0,334*
	Mustaqillik	0,452*
	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,363*

Natijalarni baholash	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	0,637**
Mustaqillik	O'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi	-0,369*

Izoh: * $r \leq 0,05$, ** $r \leq 0,01$.

Umumo'rtta ta'lim maktablari pedagoglarida o'z ustida ishlash faoliyatini tarbiyalashning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari bo'yicha o'z-o'ziga munosabat va o'z xulq-atvorini tartibga solish so'rovnomalaridan olingan natijalar shuni namoyon qildiki, shkalalar o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqador faktorlar orasidagi korrelyatsiyalar ko'proq o'z-o'zini idora qilish shkalasi o'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi ($r=0,336$, $r \leq 0,05$), o'z-o'zini qabul qilish ($r=0,315$, $r \leq 0,05$), mustaqillik ($r=0,435$, $r \leq 0,05$), natijalarni baholash ($r=0,396$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,581$, $r \leq 0,01$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'ziga munosabatning aks etishi shkalasi o'z-o'zini qabul qilish ($r=0,368$, $r \leq 0,05$), o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash ($r=0,391$, $r \leq 0,05$), mustaqillik ($r=0,344$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,374$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash shkalasi rejalashtirish ($r=0,403$, $r \leq 0,05$) va natijalarni baholash ($r=0,342$, $r \leq 0,05$) va mustaqillik ($r=0,446$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, o'z-o'zini qabul qilish shkalasi rejalashtirish ($r=0,413$, $r \leq 0,05$), natijalarni baholash ($r=0,511$, $r \leq 0,01$) va mustaqillik ($r=0,326$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, rejalashtirish shkalasi natijalarni baholash ($r=0,334$, $r \leq 0,05$) mustaqillik ($r=0,452$, $r \leq 0,05$) va o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,363$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlari bilan, natijalarni baholash shkalasi o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,637$, $r \leq 0,01$) faktorlari bilan, mustaqillik shkalasi o'z-o'zini boshqarishning umumiy darajasi ($r=0,369$, $r \leq 0,05$) faktorlar orasida yuqori darajada korrelyatsion aloqalarga kirishganligi namoyon bo'lgan.

Iroda va xarakterni shakllantirishda o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash. O'qituvchilik faoliyatida o'qituvchi xarakteri muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bunda iroda, his-tuyg'ularini boshqarish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'zini- o'zi tarbiyalash ma'lum natijalarga olib kelishi lozim. Bunda: o'zini idora eta olish, yaxshi kayfiyat, o'ziga buyruk berish, ishontirish, shaxsiy rejimga rioya qilish va o'z koidasiga ega bo'lish lozim sanaladi.

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**BUKHARA PROVINCE IN THE TERRITORY THE SUN FROM ENERGY
USAGE OPPORTUNITIES RESEARCH**

Safarov Alisher Bekmurodovich

*associate professor, department of "Energoaudit" " Bukhara Engineering-
Technological Institute*

O'Imasov Quدرات Norqul o'g'li

*Doctoral student, department of "Energoaudit" Bukhara Engineering-
Technological Institute*

Abstract. *This in the article Bukhara province of the territory yearly consumption who does electricity energy pointers and the sun from energy use possibilities analysis given. In the region The amount of solar radiation directly falling on the earth during the year was estimated. According to this, it was determined that the amount of horizontal solar radiation is approximately $4,55 \frac{\text{GWh}}{\text{m}^2 \text{ km}}$. It has been researched that if we fully use solar panels, the technical potential of the region is 41 TWh/year, and the technical potential of solar thermal energy (for the case where the technical capacity of collectors is 80% (EIK) is 184 TWh/year.*

Key words: *solar energy, electricity consumption, solar panels, solar radiation, technical potential of solar energy, solar collectors.*

Introduction. The experience of world development shows that the improvement of society's living conditions is closely related to the increase in energy consumption and the understanding of the need for its rational use. Therefore, the fuel energy complex of any country is not only the leading sector of the national economy, but also has an important impact on the social development of the society.

Strengthening the energy security of the country in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2023 PQ -57 "On measures to accelerate the introduction of renewable energy sources and energy-saving technologies in 2023" , to diversify the part of the fuel and energy balance related to the production of electricity, thermal energy and biogas using renewable energy sources, to introduce innovative technologies, scientific and technical developments in the field of using renewable energy sources, to increase the energy efficiency of renewable energy sources devices , encouraging the expansion and localization of their production, giving preference and benefits in the field of using renewable energy sources is one of the great achievements in the field of using renewable energy sources in our region [1].

In world practice, more attention is now being paid to the use of renewable, alternative energy sources such as sunlight, wind, biomass, geothermal, sea and ocean water waves, along with traditional energy sources. Among them, the sun occupies an important place. Through the use of various technologies, solar energy can already cover a large part of the current energy demand.

Bukhara region is located in the southern 39.77° latitude and western 64.48° longitude of Uzbekistan, its total area is 39.4 thousand km^2 or 9% of the territory of the Republic. In the Bukhara region, the economic sphere includes agriculture, industry, transport, construction, and communal household services. The annual electricity consumption of the region in the economic sphere is equal to 3410495 thousand kWh (as of 2018). Figure 1 shows the structure of electricity consumption by economic sectors in Bukhara region.

Electricity consumption in the region is higher in summer, the main reason for which is the extensive use of pumping equipment for irrigation of agricultural land. Electricity consumption of existing water pumps in the region is more than 50% of the total electricity consumption. With the development of small business and entrepreneurship in the economic sectors of Bukhara region, the demand for electricity is also increasing. Bukhara region consumed 3410.5 MWh of electricity in 2018 [2]. This indicator is 12% more than in 2014.

Figure 1. Distribution of electricity in economic sectors of Bukhara region.

One of the main problems in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in remote areas of Bukhara region is continuity and reliability of electricity. It is necessary to assess the possibilities of using renewable energy sources in ensuring energy security and continuity in these regions.

Among the renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan, the potential of solar energy is several times greater than the total energy sources.

The gross solar energy potential of Uzbekistan is 5073 mln. tne, and the technical potential is 176.8 mln. estimated to be equal to tne. So, the solar energy that falls on the land of Uzbekistan in one year is much more than the verified hydrocarbon raw materials of the country according to the absolute value. Currently, only 0.3% of solar energy is used.

The amount of direct solar radiation falling on the earth during the year (W/m^2) [3].

Table 1

breadth	Hour moon	12 ⁰⁰	11 ⁰⁰ 13 ⁰⁰	10 ⁰⁰ -14 ⁰⁰	9 ⁰⁰ -15 ⁰⁰	8 ⁰⁰ -16 ⁰⁰	7 ⁰⁰ -17 ⁰⁰	6 ⁰⁰ -18 ⁰⁰
$\varphi=40^\circ$	january	823.6	777.2	730.8	6244	359.6	-	-
	December	870	858.4	798.4	7108	533.6	-	-
	February	904.8	883.2	846.8	7772	754	371.2	-
	November	928	916.4	887.4	8468	742.4	598.6	1972
	March	928	916.4	887.4	846.	777.2	632.2	3944
	October	930	904.8	883.2	846.8	777.2	678.6	510.4
	April							
	September							

As can be seen from table 1, let's say at noon, the energy of the sun's rays falling on each square meter of the surface is equal to the heat released by a 1kW electric plate. In short, the energy released by the sun in 1 minute is enough to evaporate all the water on the globe, this energy $19 \cdot 10^{14}$ is equal to the amount of energy released when a ton of oil is burned. Humanity can use such a huge source of energy for another 40 billion years.

The territory of Bukhara region is considered a sunny country, and there is sufficient potential for using solar energy.

The gross (theoretical) potential of solar energy of the region is the energy of the annual average solar radiation of the region that falls on the region in one year.

The sun of energy gross potential the following expression through defined as :

$$W = ES(l)$$

Here : the value of the annual solar energy falling E –on the surface, S –the surface of the area.

of the region the sun of energy technical potential is a science and of technique present development level and ecological to standards according to respectively year during the sun from radiation removable average long term total energy _

The sun of energy technical potential two type our separation can :

- heat of energy technical potential .
- the sun of radiation belongs to conversion as a result received electricity of energy technical potential .

Figure 2. Bukhara of the region months in the section maximum, minimal and average temperature (°C).

According to the data received from the weather station, the amount of horizontal solar radiation in the territory of Bukhara region $\frac{kWh}{m^2 \text{ kun}}$ is approximately 4.55. The average annual temperature °C is 14.2-16.5. In the summer months, the temperature rises to 40-50 degrees °C. Sunny days in the region are 2930-3000 hours. According to the analyzed data, annual solar radiation is 1710-1880 kWh/m². This, in turn, increases the efficiency of using solar energy.

Summary by doing to say if we If we fully use solar panels with an efficiency of 18% in the regions of Bukhara region, the technical potential of the region will be equal to 41 TWh/year. This is the present Bukhara in the area used from energy one how many even high that means of the province the sun heat of energy technical potential (of collectors technical possibilities FLK was 80% case for) 184 TWh / year per year energy get possible we have [4].

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**BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF MATEMATIKA DARSLARIDA RAQAMLI
TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHART-
SHAROITLARI.**

Xodiyeva Gulhayo Hasan qizi

Toshkent amaliy fanlar universiteti o'qituvchisi.

gxodiyeva@inbox.ru

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezisda boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati, dars samaradorligini oshirish vositalari hamda uning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Elektron resurslar, raqamli texnologiyalar, multimediya, axborot texnologiyalari, matematik dunyoqarash.*

Abstract: *This thesis discusses the importance of using digital technologies in elementary mathematics classes, means of improving lesson efficiency, and its pedagogical conditions.*

Key words: *Electronic resources, digital technologies, multimedia, information technologies, mathematical outlook.*

Bugungi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish sur'atini hisobga olib ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirishga harakat qilinarkan, bevosita zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari, raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishga bugungi kunda talab oshib bormoqda. Hozirgi vaqtda ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etishda asosiy diqqat samarali multimediyali darslarni ishlab chiqarishga qaratilmoqda. Xalqaro tajribalarga tayangan holda tekstografik elektron mahsulotlar o'rniga interaktiv, multimediya manbalariga boy elektron resurslar qabul qilinmoqda. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida qo'llaniladigan darsliklarning interaktivligi, multimediya manbalariga boyligiga asosiy e'tiborni qaratish lozim. Hech kimga sir emaski, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari multimediyali hamda kreativlik asosida tashkil etilgan darslarga juda katta qiziqish bildiradilar.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish o'qituvchilarga o'qitishning metodini, tashkiliy shaklini va mazmunini sifatli o'zgartirish imkonini beradi. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida pedagogik faoliyat vositalari takomillashtirilmoqda, o'qitish sifati va samaradorligi ortib bormoqda. Shu bilan birgalikda raqamli texnologiyalar an'anaviy o'qitish vositalariga nisbatan juda ko'p afzalliklarga ega. Raqamli ta'lim resurslarining maqsadi axborot jamiyatida o'quvchilarning intellektual imkoniyatlarini mustahkamlash, shuningdek, ta'lim tizimining barcha bosqichlarida ta'lim sifatini oshirishdan iborat. Matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning quyidagi asosiy pedagogik maqsadlarini ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin:

- zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llash orqali o'quv jarayonining barcha darajalarini faollashtirish (o'quv jarayonining samaradorligi va sifatini oshirish; fanlararo aloqalarni chuqurlashtirish; kerakli ma'lumotlarni qidirish hajmini oshirish va optimallashtirish; kognitiv faoliyat faolligini oshirish;

-matematika darslarida multimediyali vositalaridan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarning matematik bilim va dunyoqarashlarini rivojlantirish, matematik bilimlarini haqiqiy hayotda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini oshirish;

- o'quvchilarning mantiqiy hamda ijodiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish, shaxsni axborot jamiyatida qulay hayotga tayyorlash (har xil fikrlash turlarini rivojlantirish; kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish; kompyuter grafikasi, multimedia texnologiyasidan foydalanish orqali estetik tarbiya; axborot madaniyatini shakllantirish, axborotni qayta ishlash qobiliyati).

Dars bosqichlarida, asosiy o'qitish ta'siri va nazorati kompyuterga o'tkazilganda, o'qituvchi o'quvchilarni kuzatish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Bu o'qituvchiga o'z boshqaruv faoliyatini loyihalash va o'quvchilarning bilim olishga ijodiy munosabatini bosqichma-bosqich rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlarini o'quvchilarning qobiliyatlarini aniqlash va rivojlantirishga, va matematika fanini chuqur o'rganish istagini oshirishga yordam berishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, matematika darslarida multimediali o'quv kurslarini tayyorlashda ulardan foydalanish davomiyligini hisobga olish zarur. Zamonaviy o'quv multimedia matematika darsi – video va audio materiallar bilan boyitilgan matnli interaktiv materialgina bo'lmay, undagi o'quv materiallari turli shakllar va matematik topshiriqlar joylashtirilishi kerak.

Shu bilan birgalikda boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarni dastlabki geometrik shakllar bilan tanishtirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish yuqori samaradorlikka ega. O'quvchilar ushbu shakllarni ekranda 3D shaklda ko'rish orqali geometriyaning dastlabki elementlari haqida aniq tasavvurga ega bo'ladilar.

Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishda quyidagi pedagogik shart-sharoitlarga e'tibor berilish lozim:

– Raqamli texnologiya asosida o'quvchilarni matematik masalalarni tanqidiy-tahliliy yondashuv asosida hal qilishga yo'naltirish;

– O'quvchilarning matematik mantiqiy fikrlashlarini o'stirish;

– O'quvchilarning diqqatini turli vaziyatlar va holatlar tahliliga qaratish;

– Multimediyali darslarni matematik tajribalar va mashqlar o'tkazishga mo'ljallash;

–O'quvchilarni yangiliklarni izlash va topishga yo'naltirish.

Shu bilan birgalikda boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishda quyidagi talablarga alohida to'xtalib o'tish zarur;

–Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tayyorlangan ko'rgazmali vositalarning davomiyligi;

- Raqamli texnologiyalarning dars mazmuniga muvofiqligi;
- Raqamli texnologiyalarning o'quvchilarning bilim darajasiga mosligi;
- Multimedia vositalarining o'quvchilar kreativligi oshirishiga yo'naltirilganligi;

Xulosa. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida mustaqil o'rganishni ta'minlovchi va bilimlarni amaliyotda o'tkazishga yo'naltirilgan o'quv materiallarini ishlab chiqish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu o'quv matreallariga: yo'naltiruvchi matnlar, loyihalar va modullarni misol qilish mumkin. Bu o'quv materiallari o'quvchilarni mustaqil bilim olish, ijodiy fikrlash va mehnat faoliyatiga yo'naltirilgan bo'ladi. Matematik o'quv materiallari o'quvchilarning fanga tegishli faoliyat usuli bo'yicha nazariy ma'lumotlar bilan bir qatorda yetarli bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lishlari uchun turli xildagi, hajmdagi va murakkablikdagi savol va topshiriqlar tizimini qamrab olishi kerak. Ijodiy topshiriqlar tarkibiga ijodiy mashq, ijodiy mustaqil ish, turli didaktik o'yinlar kiradi. Agar ijodiy mashq vositasida o'rganilgan bilimlar yangi o'quv holatlariga tatbiq qilinsa, ijodiy mustaqil ishlardan yangi xulosalar chiqarish hamda yangicha faoliyat usullarini faoliyatda qo'llash bilan ajralib turadi. Yuqoridagi barcha fikrlardan kelib chiqqan holda, matematika darslarida raqamli texnologiyalarini ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash, bir tomondan, o'quvchilarning matematik bilimlarni o'zlashtirishini oshirishga, ikkinchi tomondan, o'quvchilarning o'z ustida mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalarini oshirish kabi imkoniyatlarni yaratadi. Bularning barchasi boshlang'ich sinf matematika o'quv jarayonini takomillashtirishga va uning samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan vositalardir.

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NEW APPROACH IN EDUCATION

Azimov Farkhod Abdikhalimovich

Teacher of the Faculty of Military Education of Fergana State University

Annotatsiya: *As our President noted: "The more educated our children get out of school, the faster the economic sectors based on high technologies will develop, the more social problems will be solved." Therefore, if I say that the threshold of New Uzbekistan starts from the school, I think that our entire nation will support this idea."*

Key words: *New Uzbekistan, reforms, higher education, reforms*

Today, all spheres of the life of New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the education system, which is considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, practical work on organizing all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country.

As our President noted: "The more educated our children are, the faster the economic sectors based on high technologies will develop, the more social problems will be solved." Therefore, if I say that the threshold of New Uzbekistan starts from the school, I think that our entire nation will support this idea."

Reforms in the higher education system constitute the main part of the reforms implemented in the field of education. In particular, the decree of the head of our state dated October 8, 2019, in order to determine the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training independent thinking highly qualified personnel to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education, to develop social spheres and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies. The concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by

This document was based on tasks such as the development of integration of science, education and production in order to accelerate intellectual development, train competitive personnel, effectively organize scientific and innovative activities, and strengthen international cooperation.

The content of the concept reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. In it, expansion of the level of coverage and improvement of the quality of education in higher educational institutions, introduction of digital technologies and educational platforms, involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of innovative structures, commercialization of scientific research results, international recognition and many other specific directions are defined. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality.

MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE TEACHING SOLUTIONS

Today, it is no secret that the world's prestigious higher education institutions are considered to be the major hotbeds of science. Currently, new higher educational institutions and branches of the world's leading universities are being established. For example, in the last 5 years, 47 new higher education institutions, including branches of foreign universities, were established in our country, and the number of higher education institutions reached 125.

Non-governmental higher education institutions are being established on the basis of the public-private partnership system. Based on the opinion of the population, part-time and evening forms of education have been restored, admission quotas are being increased. The enrollment rate of school graduates in higher education increased from 9 percent in 2016 to 25 percent in 2020.

A mechanism has been created to ensure that professors-teachers can improve their skills and undergo internships in higher education and scientific-research institutions abroad. Their monthly salary was increased by an average of 2.5 times compared to 2018. Since this year, 10 higher education institutions have been transferred to the self-financing system.

The number of state grants for higher education has been increased by at least 25%, and the number of grants for girls from needy families has been doubled to 2,000 for admission to higher education institutions.

One of the most important innovations in the education system was the transfer of 65 academic lyceums to higher educational institutions in order to strengthen the cohesion between universities and the lower levels of the education system, as well as the attachment of 187 technical schools to related universities and network enterprises.

To conclude, the promising tasks implemented in the field of education are not inferior to the reforms in other fields in terms of their relevance and practical importance. Because it is the demand of the times to continue the reforms in this field on a larger scale.

In the 21st century, which is called the age of information technology, development of science and creation of innovations in this regard has become a vital necessity in order to create high progress in all aspects of life - industry, construction, chemistry, agriculture, textiles, mechanical engineering and other fields. This process is now recognized in all developed countries in the world. Special attention is paid to this process in our republic.

It is not by chance that the President of our country started his activities as a leader with a meeting with academicians, leading scientists, people of science in general, and focused on harmonizing the development of science with the development of production in our country.

The development of the concept of the development of the concept of "Development of science until 2030" of the head of our state after that to improve the

health care system, develop the system of printing and distribution of book products, increase reading, establish new free economic zones in the republic, implement the strategy of actions for further development of the country, The establishment of the International Center of Imam Termizi and many other decisions, decrees, and orders regarding the promotion of science as one of the main issues was a practical expression of this attention.

Safe protection of intellectual property is of particular importance in the process of developing science and innovation, turning their achievements into products with high added value.

According to data, the share of intellectual property is 45 percent of the gross domestic product in Europe, 12 percent in China, and 7 percent in Russia. The meeting chaired by our President on October 12, 2020 was also dedicated to the topic "Protection of intellectual property - serves as a reliable foundation for the Third Renaissance". At that time, the head of our state paid special attention to the need to ensure cooperation between patent owners and entrepreneurs.

In particular, one of the most important documents adopted in the education system was the adoption of the new version of the Law "On Education". Based on this law, the main principles, educational system, types and forms in the field of education were clearly defined.

Also, according to the law, state higher education, secondary special, professional educational institutions and their branches, higher, secondary special, professional educational organizations with state participation and their branches are established by the decisions of the President or the government. Establishment of non-state educational institutions was determined to be carried out by their founders. The license to non-state educational organizations will be issued by the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education.

Accordingly, we can say that the adoption and implementation of this Law was one of the most important documents adopted in the field of education.

In recent years, the reforms implemented in the field of education in Uzbekistan are consistently implemented at Namangan State University. Consequently, in the next three years, the number of faculties was increased from 9 to 15, the number of specialty departments was increased from 27 to 46, the number of nutrition areas was increased from 31 to 52, and the number of master's degrees was increased from 12 to 26. Accordingly, the number of young university students with a desire for science increased from 5,100 to 21,000.

The number of professors increased from 470 to 710. Until the 2018-2019 academic year, the university has 26 faculties, and no specialized council has been operating. In recent years, great attention has been paid to the training of scientific pedagogues, the scientific potential has increased by 37 percent, and today 9 specialized councils are operating in 12 specialties to ensure the quality of education.

MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE TEACHING SOLUTIONS

Of course, in this regard, the goal of filling the ranks of university scientific-pedagogical personnel with potential personnel has been determined at the expense of doctoral students studying at 17 basic doctoral programs.

Until recently, the university mainly trained specialists for the pedagogical field. Today, at the university, the organization and management of institutions of Archeology, Culture and Art, Sociology, Jurisprudence (by types of activities), Library and information activities (by types of activities), Zooengineering: fisheries, Fruit growing and viticulture, Cultivation and processing technology of medicinal plants, Vegetable farming, policing and potato growing, organization and management of greenhouses, social work (in various fields of activity), organization and management of hotels, tourism (in areas of activity) it shows that it is becoming the intellectual center of our region in the real sense.

The university, as a major scientific and research center, will establish a media center at Namangan State University, establish an educational and practical training course on Aquaculture, "Preparation of medicinal drinks from medicinal plants", production technology of curative preventive sumac, rare, endangered and endemic species distributed in the Fergana Valley. is participating in major international scientific projects, such as creating a living collection of species, an electronic photo album, and a digitized electronic database.

On the initiative of the President, the granting of academic and organizational, as well as financial independence for higher education organizations and the expansion of the powers of the Councils, the implementation of the state policy in the field of education, the provision of quality education services and the full fulfillment of the tasks given by our government in this regard, potential personnel who determine the development of our country creates ample opportunities for preparation

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THE BENEFITS OF FRENCH NATIONAL CUISINE FOR THE HUMAN ORGANISM

Halimova Makhbuba Turakulovna

1st School higher category French language teacher

The French are known for their delicious cheese, crusty baguettes, and rich wines. Despite these indulgences, the French tend to have lower rates of coronary heart disease deaths than other countries. Why might this be? Read on to learn the health benefits of the French diet. Then, try it for yourself by downloading our free, seven-day French meal plan menu created by a Registered Dietitian.

Compared to American eating habits, the French diet relies on small portions of high-quality foods eaten less often. Across restaurant portion sizes, individual portions in grocery stores, and recommended portion sizes in cookbooks, French portion sizes are significantly smaller than American portion sizes. Despite eating less than Americans, the French spend more time at their meals, which helps them feel more satisfied.

French cuisine requires eaters to enjoy quality over quantity. For example, in our French meal plan, you'll enjoy 4oz of rich crème brûlée as opposed to several handfuls (or more) of a lesser-quality candy bar or sweet. Eating the good stuff in smaller portions can help curb cravings and make you feel more satisfied.

Traditional French cuisine includes butter, bread, and many other "non-diet" foods. However, in addition to eating smaller portion sizes, the French spend more time eating than their American counterparts. By slowly enjoying the taste and textures of real food, the French end up having more "food experience." This concept helps the French feel more satisfied by the end of the meal, despite eating less than Americans.

For a practical and flavorful tour of French cuisine, try our free, weeklong French meal plan. From shrimp provencal and traditional French onion soup to ratatouille and French pastries, you'll enjoy the flavors of one of the great food capitals of the world. To get the true experience, incorporate some French eating habits by slowing down at meals, eating smaller portion sizes, and taking your time to savor each dish.

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**A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF
PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS MEANING "LIFE" AND "DEATH" IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK LANGUAGES.**

Boboqulova Gulasal Bobir qizi

English teacher at the school 72 th of Yunsabad district

Abstract: *The scientific research shows that the problem of existence and non-existence is one of the keys in philosophy, that existence is existence before non-existence, existence has objective and subjective reality, the worlds that exist and will exist, materiality and ma It refers to general concepts that include spirituality, past and future, death and life, soul and body.*

Keywords: *philosophy, life, death, past, future, soul, body, concept, universe, existence.*

Philosophy of life (German : Lebensphilosophie) is a philosophical current that studies and interprets the problems of the meaning, purpose, and value of life. It appeared in Germany and France in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. A. Schopenhauer stands at the beginning of the philosophy of life, and F. Nietzsche is its founder. According to the representatives of the stream, life is the first reality, and then it is an integral whole, which is divided into spirituality and materiality, consciousness and being. Life is the main concept of the philosophy of life. The philosophy of life seeks to understand the essence of life itself. He glorifies feelings and instincts, criticizes and denies reason. According to supporters of the philosophy of life, the concept of life is complex, ambiguous, and has no clear interpretation. Therefore, there is a natural-biological (F.Nietzsche , A.Klages), cultural-historical (V.Dilthey, G.Zimmel, O.Spengler, H.Ortega i-Gaset) understanding of it. In the natural-biological interpretation, life is understood in a biological sense, and biological properties are applied to the whole reality. Life is compared to naturalness and opposed to any artificiality. Supporters of this trend glorify power, connect the realization of any idea with the interests of people or social groups. According to K.Bergson , life is a spatial vital intensity, which is initially born in a single center and develops in parallel through a series of explosions, qualitative jumps, which differ from each other in many respects. Its essence is consciousness or superconsciousness, which arises from inner experiences and is understood through processes in the soul. Dilthey, Simmel look for the essence of life in inner spiritual experiences. Ortega-i-Gaset points out that the mind that seeks to study human life by comparison with nature is weak for such research. He also tries to develop a relatively broad understanding of the mind, which takes into account the unity of man and the universe, the fact that human life is independent of external influences and has its own origin. Despite such point-oriented thoughts, life appears in them as an organic

process of creative formation that opposes mechanical, irregular structures, all fixed determinations and rigidities.

Creativity, especially artistic creativity, is extremely important to the philosophy of life, it is even life itself. At this point, the philosophy of life approaches non-rational intuitionism, its theory of knowledge. For example, the fact that the dynamics of life, the individual nature of things cannot be expressed in general concepts, it can be directly understood and understood through intuition is characteristic of both streams. The philosophy of life sees a sharp difference in the way science and philosophy approach the world. Science tries to conquer and subjugate the world, and philosophy is characterized by observation, which makes it close to art. Mind is by its very nature cut off from life; intellectual knowledge and the science based on it can understand only the relations between things, not things. Rational knowledge is aimed at the satisfaction of purely practical interests, the expediency that brings benefits. Non-intellectual, intuitive, symbolic ways of understanding life are contrasted with scientific knowledge. A work of art, especially poetry, music is a means of understanding life and expressing it relatively accurately.

Life, death and the meaning of human life are philosophical issues because no one can explain these words and events. No one can prove life or death and things that exist. Death is terrifying and at the same time fascinating, it has so many mysteries that we can never guess. You can spend your whole life thinking about it, trying to understand and explain it. To solve this, we can only meet him and lose our lives because we meet death, so until death is not known until now. You will know how many people died every hour, every day, month, year. What does death look like for us? Death comes to us in the form of old age or in the form of climatic events, in the form of an accident or in the form of a knife in the back or the heart. Death is different and how we deserve it determines how our life is lived, how valuable or inferior it is.

What if death is death, life itself dies? And if death in the form of life is easier and easier than our life. And we should cling to our life like the last drop of our life and try for at least an hour, rather we should prolong our life and not see death. If our sinful souls are punished and sentenced to life as a prisoner in a strict regime colony. After all, life is sometimes like a punishment, in the form of life problems.

Death is the beginning of a new life, and another is meant for us or we have lost. It is not for nothing that the phrase "life after death" appeared. And death is the door to a new life. We are afraid of death, and fear is inherent in us because we are always afraid of the unknown. We must survive death in order to have eternal life. We are afraid of death because we believe that we are what we are. We are death.

In philosophy, the problem of life and death is one of the important keys of man. Death occurs as a result of the dying process. Like any biological organism, man dies, but unlike other animals, he understands his death. This makes him think about the

meaning of life and death. All philosophical views are conditionally divided into two types:

1. There is no life after death . After death, along with the human body, his soul and mind disappear.
2. Life after death . A religious-idealistic approach, life on earth is a preparation for the hereafter.

Philosophers have debated about "existence" and "non-existence" since ancient times. They wrote many works about the origin, essence, characteristics and forms of existence. So what is existence? Although this question seems very simple at first glance, it has not yet been found an answer that satisfies all people. This situation is explained by the existence of views on existence from different points of view. For example, some philosophers explain existence by connecting it with materiality, material things. According to their point of view, existence is a concept that encompasses only objective reality. In that case, they answer the question that thoughts, human thinking, thoughts are excluded from the concept of existence, that such concepts are derived from objective reality. The part of philosophy that explains the doctrine of existence is called ontology . (This concept was first used in philosophy by H. Wolff). This branch of philosophy studies the issues of the universe and existence. Absence means nothing. Nothingness is the beginning and the end of everything, which brings everything into nothingness. In this sense, nothingness is one with infinity, endlessness, and eternity. Where non-existence recedes, existence appears. Therefore, both the creator and the cause of existence is non-existence. Nothing compares to nothingness. There is no answer to the question of what is absence in science. There are several concepts of existence. It is known from history that philosophers have put forward different ideas about existence. In the Zoroastrian doctrine, which arose in the soil of Central Asia, it was believed that existence is a product of the sun and fire, and the burning fire is the main essence of existence. Because, according to this idea, fire is the basis of any change and movement, and it gives existence to existence. The ancient Greek philosopher Socrates compares existence with knowledge, and he believes that something exists only if we know it, and that the wider a person's knowledge , the wider the existence.

Democritus, a scientist of the ancient world, explained that existence consists of a complex of atoms. According to him, the essence of existence lies in its existence. What does not exist is non-existence. In the teachings of Islam, existence is a divine reality. That is, he is an existence created by Allah. In this regard, there were teachings of unity and unity. Islamic thinkers developed the doctrine of existence in many ways.

Existence is a general concept that encompasses objective and subjective reality, existing and future worlds, materiality and spirituality, past and future, death and life, soul and body. The people around us, the world, nature, society, our thoughts,

ideas, and thoughts all exist at the same time, they are manifested in different ways and in different ways, and all of them are summarized under the sign of existence and enter into the concept of existence. Existence is a broader concept than existence and reality. Existence is the part of existence that is manifested in the present moment, and the concepts of existence include past and future things and events. Reality is the part of existence that is known to everyone and recognized by them. In traditional philosophical views, three areas of existence are distinguished. They include: existence of nature, existence of society, existence of consciousness. The most common sign for these is their presence.

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MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INNOVATIVE TEACHING SOLUTIONS
 STUDY FOR USING OF NATIONAL VALUES FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL
 TEACHERS

Bababekova Nigora Ismailovna

Director of non-state educational institution "Five plus 5+"

Annotation. *The scientific research illustrates that the moral decadence among primary school pupils that inculcation of national values in primary pupils, methods of teaching adopted by teachers and moral value subjects available in primary school curriculum in Uzbekistan. The aim of this study is to determine the role and importance of values education with the spiral of education administrator, teacher and curriculum. In this general purpose, school managers and teachers' opinions about the role given values education in curriculum and recommendations on values education to be effective, teachers' importance about values education, activities about values education in schools and importance of value education were evaluated. At present time, experiencing a rapid change in all aspect of life, material and spiritual culture of societies have been changing. This change between material and spiritual culture without against spiritual culture in other words changing without cultural delay is an indicator of healthy development of societies.*

Keywords: *curriculum, primary school, national value, pupils, spiritual values.*

In general, the development is adversely affected in societies, ahead of the change in material culture. Therefore, attention should be given to specific areas in order to live equal change and support two cultures mutually. The first of all these areas is values education. Over the years, several methods have been put in place to enhance the behavior of pupils at the primary level all over the world. A guide to shape both the pupils' and teachers' behavior was introduced. The primary school teachers were selected using simple random sampling and judgmental techniques. A self-designed questionnaire titled "Inculcating National Values in Primary School Pupils" (INVP) was adapted and used with four distinct sections. Data collected were analyzed and the research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The study revealed that the extent of moral decadence was high despite the inclusion of the subjects that could teach moral values in the school curriculum. Moral values were not adequately taught in the sampled primary schools. Pictures, discussions and role play methods with the aid of textbooks were used in teaching national values. The study concluded by recommending that parents should inculcate moral values into homes as schools build on the foundation set by the homes. Appreciating good actions and demonstrations by role models were seen to be the best methods of inculcating national values in primary school pupils.

It can also be said to be the acceptable principles or standards of a group of people. Some of the core values are honesty, tolerance, justice, respect, happiness, forgiveness, self-control, humanness, equality, humility, moderation, love, truthfulness and trust amongst others. Contrary to what the society was like; a safe haven where peace and tranquility reigned, children were free to play outside their compounds without fear of being away from their place of residence, neighbors could be trusted to take care of the children while the parents are away; it appears that values have lost. Indiscipline, dishonesty, injustice, disrespect, unpatriotic, moral and spiritual decadences have become the order of the day. This study was a descriptive survey research design which was non-experimental in nature. This design was adopted to describe the existing situation by meeting the subjects in their natural settings.

Figure 1. Schematic views on analysis about the beliefs on values education's importance

Thanks to the qualitative analysis, model is located in Figure 1. Besides, the number of attribution and the views of teachers and administrators about the importance of values education are located in Figure 1. In addition to this, opinions, obtain from believing about importance of values education, are given with details below, these are loadings (the number of references made to the theme) that maximum number of loads and opinions in these themes. The most part of teachers

and directors in this study say that teachers give importance for value education. Samples and sub-themes are below. Model formed based on the analysis regarding the importance teachers and directors give to the value education are shown Figure 2 via themes.

Figure 2. Schematic views on teachers and administrators' importance given to values education.

Harm of mass media tools, value erosion and lack of moral are real causes of the importance of value education; it is found by teachers and directors. Besides, some factors have appeared (for example: people behave personally, becoming desensitized towards actions, especially young see wrong people as a model and pushing groups that have disadvantage) and these factors cause more believe about value education.

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Kholmurodova Shahnoza Ganisher qizi

Student of Alfraganus University

Uzshano@gmail.com

Abstract. *Although art has existed in our country for many years, the interest and attention towards it among the people has decreased. As a result, there are several reasons that prevent the existing art from being brought to a sufficient regional and international scale. Also, due to a number of economic reasons, unlike folk art, the visual arts of Uzbekistan have not yet received state benefits and the work of Uzbek artists today needs support and investors.*

Key words: *art museum, art tourism, artist-tourist, art gallery, economic reasons.*

Introduction. From the literature analysis mentioned above, we can see that currently art has become a local and national income generating factor through tourism. While contributing to the economy, art tourism renews the social character of a destination. It brings together locals and tourists, increases community pride, improves arts-related organizations and creates a more vibrant place. According to the results of studies conducted by foreign scholars, we can see that 21% of international tourists travel for art tourism. This indicator is now considered sufficient for the developing art tourism.

Based on the existing factors of our country, the main emphasis is placed on museums and art galleries for the development of art tourism. Also, in recent years, a number of works have been carried out in Uzbekistan to ensure the implementation of the Law "On Museums" (No. 177 dated September 12, 2008) and to further increase the flow of tourists. More than 20 new museums have been launched in the last 5 years at the initiative of President Sh. Mirziyoyev. According to research, 35.3 million people say that an event related to art or cultural heritage has influenced their choice of destination for travel. This means that now more than ever, those involved in tourism need to invest in the arts. At the same time, through art tourism, countries

achieve the desired result by receiving tourists and helping to promote their art to the world. According to the Americans for Arts' & Economic Prosperity study, arts and culture travelers stay longer and spend more than other travelers, which has a strong economic impact on those involved in this area of tourism.

Figure 1. Things to do to develop art.

The above studies prove that art is an important factor for tourism development. According to the information, strengthening the ties between tourism and the arts will play an important role as a means of preserving and revitalizing the culture of the area. In addition, it is intended as art tourism, which is closely related to the economic, social, cultural and natural structures of the places where it is located.

In addition, there are a number of problems that need to be solved in the near future in the field of art tourism, the solution to which is the construction of new museums and exhibition facilities for large-scale collections, their popularization in publications, filling up the collections in museums, creating an electronic database, and making the available resources in this field widely available through social networks.

While the number of countries known for art tourism is increasing, Uzbekistan has also seen changes in art tourism in recent years. However, based on the above information, we can see that the state of art tourism in our country is still in its infancy. The goal of art tourism development is to update the country's image, organize modern art activities, attract art tourists through attractive art museums, galleries, exhibitions, and festivals. Art tourists don't just visit, they enhance their experience of art and discover new products and trends by combining it with the art of the destinations they visit. Similarly, art tourism also serves to broaden people's understanding and thoughts.

As part of the research, it was determined that our country has an art environment due to art museums, galleries, events and artists, and can become a country famous for art from the point of view of tourism. The main goal of our research is to develop the direction of art tourism in our country and create a new tourist art space offering a number of tourist services, including types of art activities. There is no doubt that there will be significant changes in both domestic and inbound tourism destinations through the development of this sector.

At the end of our research, we have developed a model of what needs to be done in order for Uzbekistan to join the list of highly popular art destinations such as Italy, France and Germany. According to him, based on the fact that art can be understood, expanded and exchanged in any way, in the example of our country, each province or city should be selected for the same art direction and work on it. the area should be turned into an art destination for tourists. For example, if modern art galleries and exhibition halls are increased in the city of Tashkent and the area is made a

destination of modern art, then the city of Margilon, based on its possibilities, i.e. design using satin and silk fabrics, i.e. fashion can be converted to address. Practical tours for tourists should be organized in organized areas and these destinations should be turned into "lively cities". The main result of the implementation of the project: the creation and development of a new direction of tourism in the city - Art tourism, as a result of which the flow of tourists will increase, art centers will become a source of income and make a great contribution to the economy of our country.

Concluding of the view that, art in the tourism industry allows visitors to interact and connect with the local environment. Widespread introduction of art tourism in our country among the growing tourism sectors will not only increase the flow of tourists, but also bring Uzbek art to the international level and reveal the hidden layers of art.

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**STUDYING OF THE BIOLOGICAL, PSYCHOLOGICAL, AND SOCIAL
ASPECTS OF AGING**

Abdullaev G'ofurjon Raximjonovich

Doctor of Biological Sciences Prof, Namangan State University.

Ikramova Nodira Maxmudovna

Researcher, Namangan State University.

Annotation. *Gerontology is the study of the biological, psychological, and social aspects of aging. From early beginnings in research and theory, gerontology developed into a multidisciplinary field of study and, more recently, into a professional field commonly known as the field of aging. This article identifies key factors that influenced the development of gerontology as a professional field, differentiates three categories of gerontological workers and professionals, delineates generic job roles for gerontological specialists, briefly reviews professional opportunities for gerontological specialists in several traditional fields, provides a glimpse into numerous emerging career paths, and offers recommendations necessary for further career development in the field of aging.*

Keywords: *gerontology, gerontological biology, gerontology sociology, physical, mental, and social capacities.*

Introduction. The processes of aging are complex, and combined with the uncertainties about death, a fertile ground for myth, fantasy, and wishful thinking has always existed. These speculations have given rise to myths about the prolongation of life and the nature of death, some elements of these myths have been displaced by information provided by scientific research but many still remain as part of our cultural inheritance. The word is derived from the Greek word for an old man, gerent or gerents; plus, the suffix logy, which refers to a branch of knowledge or science. The term geriatrics refers to a branch of medicine that specializes in the care and treatment of the diseases and health problems of older persons. From archeological studies of the careful entombment of persons in preliterate times it is apparent that in many cultures a great deal of thought was given to the transition from life to death and to prospects for life after death. In those cultures, care was taken in the manner of burial and in providing accompanying articles that might be useful in a future existence. Although one can only speculate about what our preliterate ancestors thought about old age and aging, their ideas were undoubtedly carried over into many of the earliest written material. While Social Gerontology has claimed its own disciplinary territory, it shares connections to various related disciplines, including those like Psychology, Sociology, Social Work, and more.

Figure 1. Fields of gerontology

We studied geriatric syndromes as the representative geriatric subject deeply associated with elderly diabetics [11]. In 175 elderly diabetics, the prevalence of disability was 35.3%, depression 28.5%, malnutrition 38.2%, and osteoporosis 20.3%. Writers are seen as credible when they present a conceptual context that draws from multiple disciplinary areas and demonstrate methodological sophistication and rigor. Papers should represent a “dialogue.” The field’s citations practices embody these values, and you can see that in the breadth of sources used, with specific citations from Gerontology sources. Citations should be purposeful, strategic, and support the writer’s argument/claim and avoid overgeneralizations, oversimplifications, and unfounded opinions. Gerontology, due to its broader focus on multiple aspects of aging own human beings is multidisciplinary, involving a number of fields. Many of which are psychology related such as therapy, social work, psychology, psychiatry, as well as focused branches such as behavioral psychology, clinical psychology, and even forensic psychology.

Figure 2. Health literacy in older persons with diabetes mellitus

Social Gerontology is a sub-field within Gerontology which is also multi-disciplinary by nature and specializes in aging older adults and aspects of living with, studying, and/or working with them in society. The main responsibility of a Social Gerontologist would be to research, educate, and advance the overall causes effecting older people.

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN Gerontology Vs Geriatrics

Figure 3. The difference between Gerontology and Geriatrics

Social factors, such as social relationships and socioeconomic circumstances, have a similarly important impact on health and well-being. We hypothesize that with the same facilities, coaching and training advice, average swimmers, for example, would produce maximum times appropriate to their abilities and that the profile of decreasing performance as a result of age would be the same as that produced by better physically endowed athletes. Aside from hypothetical elite genes there are other related issues that need to be addressed. Scientists are developing and

refining recommendations for people of all ages regarding optimal diet, use of dietary supplements, mental stimulation, physical exercise, quality sleep, social engagement, stress reduction, and other practices to increase their likelihood of enjoying healthy old age. Still other researchers are looking for better ways to enhance the physical, mental, and social capacities of older adults and to expand opportunities for them to achieve personal goals and contribute to society in meaningful ways.

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